

**LAYING THE GROUNDWORK: COMMUNITY CONTRIBUTIONS TO
ECOSYSTEM REGENERATION AND BUSINESS MODEL EMERGENCE**

A Case Study of Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland

Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT

Master's Thesis

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ABSTRACT

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Laying The Groundwork: Community Contributions to Ecosystem Regeneration and Business Model Emergence

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Nature regeneration is a critical response to biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation. Regenerative Ocean Farming offers a novel approach combining food production and ecosystem regeneration. However, the foundational role of community actor contributions in enabling ecosystem regenerative practices remains underexplored. This thesis examines the contributions of community actors in early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and how these contributions lay the foundation for regenerative business model emergence. A qualitative case study was conducted on a community-driven regenerative ocean farming initiative in Finland, focusing on experimental activities on the duck mussel species. Data was collected through seven semi-structured interviews, two field observations, supplemented by virtual meetings and discussions. Findings of this study revealed strategic community roles in early-stage regenerative practices, formation of Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge (Strategic-LEK), and the use of gastronomy as a tool for market and cultural legitimation. These contributions collectively enable conditions for ecosystem regeneration and support the co-emergence of regenerative businesses rooted in place-based ecological knowledge, social collaboration, and cultural values.

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ABBREVIATIONS

LEK	Local Ecological Knowledge
TEK	Traditional Ecological Knowledge
IEK	Indigenous Ecological Knowledge
SES	Social-Ecological Systems
LAG	Local Action Group
FLAG	Fisheries Local Action Group
ERC	Ecosystem Restoration Communities
NDC	Neighbourhood Development Centre
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
ESM	Earth System Models
LK	Local Knowledge
LTEM	Low-Trophic Extractive Mariculture

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1. Introduction

This is the first chapter of this thesis, conducted to understand the community's contribution to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices. This chapter examines the background of the study, research gap, research objective and question, delimitations, and structure, as well as a brief overview of the conceptual lens and research methods, which will be covered in more detail in the following chapters.

1.1 Background

Humanity is currently using resources equivalent to 1.75 Earths! According to the World Economic Forum, biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation are ranked the third-highest global risks (WEF, 2025). Nature is almost at its tipping point, and when it reaches this point, it is predicted to be irreversible and will potentially be disastrous for both nature and human beings (WWF, 2024). The findings of the Living Planet Report 2024 state that habitat loss and degradation were mainly driven by human food systems, followed by overexploitation, invasive species, and diseases (WWF, 2024). Nonetheless, it states that it is not too late to protect the planet, but it requires massive steps to transform the food, energy, and finance systems in order to conserve and restore nature.

This is where nature and ecosystem regeneration play their role. Ecosystem Regeneration is a co-evolutionary process where human and business activities contribute to restoring and enhancing social-ecological systems (SES) by adapting to their feedback loops, adaptive rhythms, and place-based needs (Hahn and Tampe, 2021). Sustainable businesses aim to do less harm to the planet, while regenerative businesses go beyond merely being sustainable by enabling the conditions for improving the health and vitality of the planet and people in a simultaneous and synergetic manner (Hahn and Tampe, 2021; Radjou, 2024).

Agriculture has a significant environmental impact because it consumes approximately 70% of freshwater, emits approximately one-quarter of global greenhouse gas emissions, uses half of the habitable land, and is responsible for 78% of the global ocean and freshwater eutrophication (Geneva Environment Network, 2025; Ritchie et al., 2022). As global populations grow, there is an urgent need for new food systems to enhance both people and the planet.

There is a need to think big and find alternative ways to produce food. Only 29% of the Earth is occupied by land, whereas the rest, 71%, is covered by water (NASA, 2024; Williams, 2014). This highlights the need to explore alternative ways to produce food in the water, where nutrients are abundant now. In simple terms, take the garden where there are nutrients. Marine aquaculture can support this massive stress on food systems (Jones et al., 2022).

This opens the door for “*Regenerative Ocean Farming*,” an emerging approach where aquatic food production is combined with active regeneration of the ocean (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021). Regenerative ocean farming aims to clean the water, capture carbon, and enhance biodiversity while producing food to actively restore the degraded ocean ecosystem (Cool Blue Future, 2024).

This thesis studies the Regenerative Ocean Farming initiative in the Coastal Ostrobothnia Region in Finland, which is in its formative phase (2024-2025), and is also a part of the Cool Blue (Horizon) and Cool Blue Baltic (EMFAF) projects (Cool Blue Future, 2024). This initiative is primarily driven by the members of Aktion Österbotten, a Local Action Group (LAG) and Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) (Aktion Österbotten, 2024), to explore how aquatic food production can be combined with ocean regeneration in Finland. Thus, this research discusses the contribution of community actors to the emergence of early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and regenerative business models.

1.2 Research Gap Addressed

As a novel concept, there is a growing interest in regenerative business research (Hanh and Tampe, 2021; Muñoz and Branzei, 2021) (Appendix 3), however, current literature treats community involvement and regenerative businesses as two distinct domains. There are many studies on community involvement to regenerate or restore nature (eg, Koko et al., 2024; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021, Sides, 2023) and likewise, an increasing number of literature on regenerative business aspects often focused on organizational innovation (eg, Das and Bocken, 2024; Konietzko et al., 2023; Hahn and Tampe, 2021). However, there is limited empirical research to understand the community contributions to ecosystem regenerative practices and how they impact the emergence of regenerative businesses.

This gap is evident across all regenerative efforts. Existing literature often overlooks the important work done by communities to lay the foundation for regenerative practices and the emergence of regenerative business models. There is limited research on how community contribution in these formative stages creates the necessary conditions for ecosystem regeneration and regenerative business models.

Thus, there is a crucial need to address this gap by exploring how communities might initiate, follow, participate, and/or shape these regenerative practices before any ecological outcomes or business models are established. This understanding is important to build more integrated theories of regeneration that address social, ecological, and economic transformations.

1.3 Research Objective and Question

This thesis aims to explore how community actors contribute in the early-stage phase of regenerative practices and how their contributions lay the foundation for future business model emergence. Therefore, this study seeks to bridge this gap where community involvement and regenerative business or entrepreneurship are treated as separate domains by studying how ecosystem regeneration begins through community actions, knowledge, and collaboration strategies initiated by communities, and how this lays the foundation for future regenerative businesses.

The research question of this study was formulated to address this problem, as stated below.

RQ - How do community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices, and how do their contributions lay the foundations for the emergence of regenerative business models?

In addition to the theoretical contributions, this study offers practical value for individuals involved in early regenerative practices by highlighting their significant contributions in the early development stages before there are any formal ecological or business outcomes. The objective is to contribute to both theoretical and practical aspects of regeneration, where communities are not merely recognized as participants but as driving forces moving these efforts forward.

1.4 Conceptual Lens

A conceptual lens for understanding the community contributions guides this study (Figure 4), which was not created using formalized theories but by adapting concepts identified through the literature synthesis. The lens includes two core pillars: Community Actor Roles and the Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) formation. Often, prior literature on community and the natural environment explores community involvement in restorative or regenerative practices in general terms (e.g., Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Impedovo et al., 2024; Koko et al., 2024; Maniraho et al., 2023; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021; Palmer et al., 2022). Therefore, this research specifically focuses on community contribution to early-stage regenerative practices, where it is still in its initiation and development stage.

The first pillar examines the diverse roles played by community actors that were identified through the literature synthesis (See section 2.4). This is connected with the second pillar, explaining how these community actor roles enable the generation of LEK (See section 2.5). Then it follows how these community actor roles and LEK create conditions for broader community engagement and lay the foundation for regenerative business models.

Together, these two conceptual pillars provide a lens to analyse community contribution to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and how these conditions may enable the emergence of regenerative business models in the context of Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland.

1.5 Research Methodology

The research methodology of this study is a qualitative, exploratory single case study design to understand how community actors contribute to early-stage regenerative practices and lay the foundation for the emergence of regenerative business models. This methodology was chosen because of the nature of the emerging process, where key actors in regenerative ocean farming in Ostrobothnia, Finland, engage with communities to implement Baltic aquatic ecosystem regenerative practices. The emerging regenerative ocean farming initiative in Finland was chosen as the case study due to its exploratory, novel, pre-commercial nature and its emphasis on community-driven factors.

As stated by Creswell (2009) and Yin (2014), the selected methodology of this thesis enables the researcher to analyze and understand the interpretations that people or groups make of a social or human problem, especially when the goal of the study is to reveal complex, contextual, and subjective experiences in an emerging field.

Semi-structured interviews and field observations were used as primary data collection methods. The Gioia method (Gioia et al., 2013) was used for data analysis in order to create the empirical model grounded in empirical insights (Figure 11).

In addition, before the empirical analysis, a systematic methodology was used for the screening and selection of the literature on community engagement in nature restoration and regeneration for the literature review (Appendix 1). Regenerative business-related literature was extended via snowballing. However, aligning with the abductive nature of the study, where there is an iterative movement between theory and empirical data (Saunders et al., 2016), additional literature was added after the data analysis to reflect emergent themes and to derive a more comprehensive and theory-related discussion.

1.6 Delimitations of the Study

This research focuses on the early-stage phase of a regenerative ocean farming initiative in the Coastal Region of Ostrobothnia, Finland. Therefore, this study explores the foundational work done by members of Aktion Österbotten, a Local Action Group (LAG) and Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) together with the Ostrobothnia region communities in the initial stages (Aktion Österbotten, 2024). The research focuses on early-stage development; therefore, the aim is not to fully analyse mature regenerative practices or fully developed regenerative business models. Furthermore, this research is limited to one case study that was chosen because of its novelty, exploratory, and community-driven approach, resulting in the findings being context-specific and not statistically generalizable. However, the findings offer analytical insights that may be transferable to similar initiatives.

This study specifically focuses on understanding how communities contribute and participate through roles, actions, and knowledge formation processes and does not analyse ecological outcomes or long-term business performances. This is because the case is still in its formative stages. In addition, the study does not include any formal policy perspectives

or broader national-level institution involvements because the focus is explicitly on localized community-level dynamics. These boundaries were intentionally set by the researcher to narrow the scope and gain an in-depth understanding (Creswell, 2009) of how ecosystem regenerative initiatives begin and develop at the community level.

1.7 Structure of the Study

This study follows a structure of six main chapters in order to understand the community contributions for early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and how their contributions create enabling conditions for the emergence of regenerative business models (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of the Study (Author Generated)

Chapter 1 provides the introduction to this study. It provides the background, research gap, research aim, research question, delimitations, and a brief overview of the conceptual lens, methodology, and structure of this study.

Chapter 2 presents a structured literature review, synthesizing prior literature on nature regeneration, community roles, LEK, and regenerative business approaches. Further, it includes the conceptual lens developed through the literature synthesis that guides the empirical data analysis.

Chapter 3 addresses the research design and methodology of this study. It includes a description of the case study, research philosophy, data collection and sampling methods, analysis method, and validation and reliability considerations.

Chapter 4 presents the findings of this study derived from the Gioia analysis, which includes four aggregated dimensions and one cross-cutting theme, using relevant quotes under each dimension.

Chapter 5 provides an in-depth discussion and interpretation of the findings, including novel insights developed by the researcher using the empirical data analysis.

Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the thesis by answering the research question using the empirical model developed, highlighting the theoretical contributions and practical implications, limitations, and suggesting future research directions.

2 Literature Review

This chapter covers the theoretical aspects of this study by reviewing and synthesizing relevant literature on nature regeneration, community involvement, LEK formation, and regenerative business approaches.

Figure 2. Structure of the Literature Review Chapter (Author Generated)

The aim is to provide a theoretical foundation to explore how community actors contribute to ecosystem regenerative practices, in order to understand how these contributions may lay the foundation for early-stage regenerative practices and the emergence of regenerative business models. The structure of the literature review chapter is illustrated in Figure 2.

2.1 Foundations of Regeneration: Definitions and Background

As a term, “*Regeneration*” can be defined as a system’s capacity to continually renew or remake itself (Carlson, 2011). The term initially originated from biology and natural sciences, where regeneration explains the renewing process of cells, organisms, and ecosystems to be resilient and recover from damage (Carlson, 2011; Stinner et al., 1997).

The critical concept of Regeneration in *Management and Organization literature* focuses on understanding how humans or non-humans are embedded in social-ecological systems (SES). Humans and organizations engage with SES to collaborate with nature, so that a system can regain its ability to continually self-organize and grow (Muñoz and Branzei, 2021), unlike the traditional sustainability approaches that emphasize preservation and fixation (Bocken et al., 2016). Further, Muñoz and Branzei (2021) state that regeneration is

an interconnected process because the healthy growth of one form of life is inherently connected to the flourishing of others.

Drawing from the above definitions, “*Nature Regeneration*” can be explained as a collection of methods and practices that improve the overall well-being of natural ecosystems (Das and Bocken, 2024; Hahn and Tampe, 2021). It involves the active restoration and renewal of damaged natural ecosystems, such as soil, biodiversity, marine, forests, or any other natural spaces, to allow nature to regenerate itself (Das and Bocken, 2024; Hahn and Tampe, 2021). In order to improve ecosystems, regenerative strategies place a strong emphasis on co-evolving and learning from nature through collaborative partnerships (Konietzko et al., 2023; Muñoz and Branzei, 2021), while focusing on achieving a net positive impact (Konietzko et al., 2023), by following the strategies of “Restoring, Preserving, and Enhancing” (Hahn and Tampe, 2021).

To understand business practices enhancing nature to be resilient and regenerate, it is important to understand Social-Ecological Systems (SES). SES is an integrated system of ecosystems and human society with reciprocal feedback and interdependence (Folke et al., 2010). Human activity plays an important role where human beings are considered to be deeply interconnected with nature, forming co-evolving systems (Hahn and Tampe, 2021).

This means it is not only about correcting damage already done, but also actively improving and enabling the conditions needed for natural ecosystems to regenerate. As human survival is deeply dependent on a healthy biosphere, nature regeneration aims to establish new methods that support the flourishing of all living beings (Konietzko et al., 2023). Therefore, this needs a paradigm shift in how societies and businesses interact with the environment to actively heal the ecological damage and promote nature’s ability to renew itself.

2.2 Role of Business in Nature Regeneration

Businesses play an important role in nature regeneration because they have a significant impact on the environment and they highly depend on the natural resources (Hahn and Tampe, 2021). Konietzko, Das and Bocken (2023, p.375), define regenerative business models as,

“Models (that) focus on planetary health and societal wellbeing. They create and deliver value at multiple stakeholder levels, including nature, societies, customers, suppliers and partners, shareholders and investors, and employees through activities promoting regenerative leadership, co-creative partnerships with nature, and justice and fairness. Capturing value through multi-capital accounting, they aim for a net positive impact across all stakeholder levels.”

Similarly, Hahn and Tampe (2021, p.460) define regenerative businesses as those,

“that enhances and thrives through the health of Social-ecological systems (SES) in a co-evolutionary process.”

While Konietzko et al. (2023) highlight the stakeholder-driven approach to regenerative models, Hahn and Tampe (2021) identify these businesses within the broad systemic interactions of human and environmental well-being. As a result, these definitions imply that business involvement in regeneration extends beyond just mitigating negative consequences to actively contributing to the repair and renewal of natural and social systems.

Hahn and Tampe (2021) identified three key strategies that can be employed by businesses to contribute to nature regeneration. Restore - Returning ecosystems to their original natural healthy state (reforestation after deforestation), Preserve - Maintaining the balance of nature while adhering to environmental boundaries (Achieve Net zero impact), and Enhance - Generating a net positive impact by actively improving ecosystems.

Businesses that operate regeneratively move beyond just minimizing harm to actively repair and restore the environment and society. These business models have a holistic approach, a focus on net positive impact, and align their operations with the overall health and well-being of the planet (Das and Bocken, 2024; Drupsteen and Wakkee, 2024; Hahn and Tampe, 2021; Konietzko et al., 2023).

To better understand the role of businesses in ecosystem regeneration, several key characteristics were identified in the reviewed literature that differentiate regenerative business models from traditional approaches. Table 1 summarizes these characteristics.

Table 1. Characteristics of Regenerative Business Models

Characteristics	Description
Systems Thinking and Approach	Regenerative businesses understand that components of SES systems interact interconnectedly rather than in isolation (Hahn and Tampe, 2021).

Net Positive Impact	Regenerative businesses aim for a net positive impact going beyond net zero to actively enhance the ecosystems (Das and Bocken, 2024; Konietzko et al., 2023)
Multi-Stakeholder Value Creation	These businesses generate and deliver value for all levels of stakeholders including nature, societies, customers, suppliers and partners, shareholders and investors, and employees rather than only focusing on quantitative goals such as profit (Konietzko et al., 2023).
Regenerative Leadership	Regenerative business leaders integrate ecological awareness into decision making to encourage regeneration. For example, implementing regenerative supply chains or investing in social and natural well-being (Das and Bocken, 2024; Konietzko et al., 2023).
Co-creative Partnerships with Nature	Regenerative businesses aim to restore societies and environments, because they understand the interdependent partnerships of human and natural systems (Konietzko et al., 2023).
Justice and Fairness	Regenerative business models create justice and fairness on different levels, by promoting equality, equity, inclusion, fair value and distribution, and moving beyond anthropocentric world view (Konietzko et al., 2023).
Multi-Capital Accounting	Regenerative business models do not only focus on financial accounting but creates multi-capital accounting across various levels by net positive impact, cultural capital, and social capital (Konietzko et al., 2023).
Nature Regeneration	Regenerative business strategies aiming to improve the overall health of the environment using regenerative farming methods, restoring degraded ecosystems, conserving forests, etc (Das and Bocken, 2024).
Social Regeneration	Regenerative businesses restore human ecosystems through fair-trade policies, including local communities in these initiatives, providing fair and decent working conditions, etc (Das and Bocken, 2024).
Responsible Sourcing	Regenerative businesses utilise sourcing methods that empower and support the growth of suppliers and local communities including fair pricing, supporting small suppliers, fair compensation, etc (Das and Bocken, 2024).
Focus on Human Health and Wellbeing	Regenerative business strategies focus on producing goods and services that improve the overall health and happiness of customers (Das and Bocken, 2024).
Focus on Employees	Regenerative businesses have an employee level focus and implement strategies to improve working conditions, lives, and well-being of their employees (Das and Bocken, 2024).
Collaboration and Partnerships	Regenerative businesses prioritize collaborations with NGOs, local communities, governments, other businesses because it is not something that can be done alone (Das and Bocken, 2024).

Regenerative Principles of Organizing in Supply Chain	Regenerative businesses prioritize proportionality (balancing operations within planetary boundaries), reciprocity (mutually beneficial interactions with nature and society), and polyrhythmicity (aligning operations with natural and social cycles) when developing new supply chains or transforming current ones (Gualandris et al., 2023).
Addressing Place Based Needs	The goal of regenerative businesses is to improve the locations by often focusing on the unique ecological and social requirements of the local communities and nature (Slawinski et al., 2019).
Regeneration of Common-pool Resources	Human actors embedded in natural commons to regenerate degenerated ecosystems through a process of biocentric work. Actors understand the state and dynamics of natural commons through biophysical objects in three different ways, biophysical anomalies, equilibria and regularities. They adopt material abduction and relational intercession to cooperate and enact to choose actions for ecosystems regeneration (Albareda and Branzei, 2024).

Regenerative, sustainable, and circular businesses all aim to operate responsibly by addressing environmental and social challenges. However, they differ in their level of ambition and focus (Das and Bocken, 2024; Konietzko et al., 2023). While sustainable and circular business models are important to reduce negative impacts, regenerative business models focus on a more ambitious and holistic approach to actively repair the SES where they operate (Das and Bocken, 2024; Drupsteen and Wakkee, 2024), or further to enhance ecosystems to recover and regenerate (Hanh and Tampe, 2021). Table 2 below summarizes the key differences between these models.

Table 2. Key Differences Between Sustainable, Circular, and Regenerative Models

Business Model Type	Primary Focus	Core Strategy
Sustainable Models	Reduce the negative impacts of the business activities on the environment and society (Konietzko et al., 2023).	Follows the triple bottom line (balancing social, economic, and environmental dimensions) (Konietzko et al., 2023).
Circular Models	Manage material flows effectively to prevent environmental value loss (Drupsteen and Wakkee, 2024).	Focus on closing, slowing, and narrowing resource loops (Bocken et al., 2016).
Regenerative Models	Actively restoring and enhancing SES in a coevolving process (Hahn and Tampe, 2021).	Achieve a nature net positive impact, going beyond net zero (Konietzko et al., 2023; Muñoz and Branzei, 2021)

The literature on regenerative business provides an exciting direction to align business activities with ecological and societal well-being. However, regeneration itself does not begin with businesses. It begins in communities, ecosystems, and relationships before business models or strategies are designed. Thus, this study shifts the lens from established businesses to the early-stage contributions of community actors for regenerative practices and how these contributions may ultimately lay the foundation for future regenerative business models.

2.3 Community Involvement in Nature Regeneration

According to the literature, communities play a critical role in ensuring long-term, place-based resilience in ecosystem regeneration. Their active contribution is essential for effective, long-term, and fair outcomes in various fields, including urban ecosystem regeneration, forest restoration, marine conservation, and landscape restoration, as well as implementing these regenerative practices (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Koko et al., 2024; Maniraho et al., 2023; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021; Palmer et al., 2022). Key reasons why community involvement in regeneration is important were identified through the reviewed literature (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Key Contributions of Community Involvement in Regenerative Practices (Author Generated)

Ecological Knowledge. Local community participation is essential in regenerative practices because they have significant ecological knowledge and a place-based understanding, which is important for the success of these practices (González-Torres et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2023; Mehmood et al., 2019). This knowledge, acquired through first-hand experiences and long-term involvement with nature, is important in understanding ecosystem dynamics, species, and restoration techniques (Haq et al., 2023). Therefore, incorporating this local knowledge will ensure the long-term sustainability of these practices.

Sense of Ownership and Long-term Commitment. When communities actively engage in these nature regenerative practices, they develop a sense of ownership and caring for the ecosystems (González-Torres et al., 2024), which will be important for the long-term success and sustainability of these projects as the communities feel more responsible for the initiative. This sense of belonging will enforce accountability in maintaining these regenerative efforts.

Social Equity and Capacity Building. The capabilities, confidence, and social capital of the local communities will be increased through participation in ecosystem regenerative practices (Palmer et al., 2022). Additionally, this fosters social inclusion and equity, ensuring marginalized groups also benefit from these efforts (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024). This supports sharing resources and benefits more fairly, reducing systematic inequalities.

Avoiding Social Exclusion and Ecological Conflicts. If community engagement in the social-ecological restoration is overlooked, it may lead to environmental degradation and social exclusion (Maniraho et al., 2023). Regenerative practices cannot succeed without considering the surrounding social systems (Palmer et al., 2022). Therefore, projects that involve local communities address both ecological and socioeconomic outcomes in an interconnected manner, resulting in more holistic and fair transitions (Fox and Cundill, 2018; Maniraho et al., 2023; Woelfle-Erskine, 2018).

Multi-stakeholder Engagement and Collaborative Knowledge. Community participation not only contributes to environmental restoration but also builds strong relationships within the community as well as with external partners such as government bodies, NGOs, and researchers (Fox and Cundill, 2018; Impedovo et al., 2024; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021). This sense of connection and collectiveness enhances the impact of the efforts, making participatory mechanisms more effective and meaningful. These community

engagements will lead to more improved and productive outcomes because of the combined knowledge of scientific and local knowledge (Impedovo et al., 2024; Mehmood et al., 2019; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021). Therefore, complex issues can be solved more creatively and effectively.

The above-mentioned community engagements will assist in continuous learning and adaptation through community feedback over time (Maniraho et al., 2023). However, the level and type of community participation depend on various factors such as the goal of the project, the background, resource availability, and the willingness of stakeholders to involve communities meaningfully (Martin et al., 2023). When communities are given genuine opportunities for active participation, ecosystem regenerative initiatives are believed to be more effective, long-lasting, and generate positive social-ecological outcomes (Fox and Cundill, 2018).

Main Outcomes. Building on these contributions and engagements, community participation in ecosystem regenerative practices results in various outcomes, such as environmental and ecological, economic, social, cultural, and governance. Table 3 provides a summary of these outcomes and key impacts across these diverse dimensions.

Table 3. Summary of Outcomes and Key Impacts of Community-led Regenerative Practices

Type of Outcome	Key Impacts
Environmental and Ecological	Biodiversity Conservation Ecosystem Restoration Climate Resilience Water Quality Improvement Habitat Restoration Healthier Ecosystems
Economic	Livelihood Diversification Regenerative Business Models Job Creation Enhanced Tourism Poverty Alleviation Increased Incomes of Farmers Empowerment of Local Businesses

Social and Cultural	<p>Enhanced Communal Unity</p> <p>Women Empowerment</p> <p>Knowledge Co-production</p> <p>Indigenous Cultural Identity Reinforcement</p> <p>Indigenous Community Empowerment</p> <p>Knowledge Sharing Across Generations</p> <p>Strengthening Community Resilience and Capacity Building</p>
Governance and Policy	<p>Community-led Policy Influence</p> <p>Participatory Governance</p> <p>Legal Advocacy and Land Use Rights</p> <p>A Rise in Ocean Literacy and Public Engagement</p> <p>Involvement of Traditional Leaders</p>

Environmental and Ecological Outcomes. Community participation in regenerative practices contributes to environmental outcomes across marine, terrestrial, and freshwater ecosystems. Community-led seaweed and bivalve farming in Bangladesh increased the quality of water, enhanced the marine ecosystems, and reduced the reliance on wild fish stocks (Ahmed et al., 2022; Asaduzzaman et al., 2024). A savanna restoration project restored 758 hectares of destroyed land, introduced 88 native species, and reduced invasive species (Montenegro et al., 2024). In the French Pyrenean Mountains, native plants were restored in degraded alpine meadows and ski slopes, enhanced vegetation management for erosion control, and local plant species were introduced for biodiversity conservation (Couix and Gonzalo-Turpin, 2015). In Intag Valley, over 75,000 trees were planted, and restored cloud forests and hydrological services (Wilson and Coomes, 2019). Seagrass restoration by the Malgana Aboriginal community improved seagrass survival rates and ecosystem recovery (Sinclair et al., 2024). In rural areas, beaver-assisted river restoration improved the recovery of wetland ecosystems, boosting aquatic biodiversity and water retention (Woelfle-Erskine, 2018). These examples demonstrate the critical role communities play in enabling regeneration across diverse ecosystems. There are numerous other studies describing similar environmental outcomes.

Economic Outcomes. In addition to environmental outcomes, various economic outcomes are created through community-led ecosystem regenerative practices. In the Loess Plateau,

afforestation efforts resulted in higher incomes for farmers, increasing rural household incomes (Qu et al., 2017). In Gahalm Gudeh, Iran, community-led regeneration practices resulted in empowering local businesses (eg, crafts manufactured by women's groups) and enhanced sustainable tourism (Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021). Seaweed and bivalve farming provided alternative income sources and created new jobs, and regenerative business models, in Bangladesh (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024, Ahmed et al., 2022). Cleanups of debris from the sea in Bali protected tourism-related income and generated new employment opportunities in environmental education and waste recycling (Koko et al., 2024). In India, indigenous communities earned daily wages, increased their livelihood through forest-based products, and aimed to develop eco-tourism in the Dering-Dibru Saikhowa Elephant Corridor (Haq et al., 2023). In Europe, Ocean and Water initiatives resulted in the creation of new jobs such as underwater gardening, the development of community-driven business models for regenerative ocean farming, and the creation of new market opportunities in a carbon-neutral blue economy (Whyte et al., 2024). These examples show how regenerative practices promote economic opportunities, leading to long-term financial sustainability for local communities.

Social and Cultural Outcomes. Further, these community-led regenerative practices resulted in social and cultural outcomes. In Bangladesh and Central Brazil, regenerative practices empowered small-scale farmers and seed collectors, especially empowering women-led initiatives. These practices also strengthened community resilience and livelihood diversification and facilitated knowledge co-production (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024, Montenegro et al., 2024). In Shark Bay, Australia, the Malgana indigenous community's seagrass restoration practices reinforced indigenous ecological stewardship and deepened their connections to nature (Sinclair et al., 2024). In Finland, co-creation in maritime spatial planning increased community involvement in marine resource management by improving stakeholder engagement, trust, and shared governance (Lähde et al., 2024). Urban ecological restoration practices improved community collaboration, unity, and increased public awareness and engagement in Rome (Impedovo et al., 2024). The involvement of younger generations in nature regeneration practices has strengthened relationships between communities and nature around the world by improving environmental knowledge, community responsibility, and collaborations (Chawla, 2023). These examples demonstrate how community-led regenerative projects empower the local

community, conserve cultural heritage, and improve social relationships in addition to regenerating ecosystems.

Governance and Policy Outcomes. Finally, these efforts result in governance and policy outcomes, ensuring long-term community participation in these practices. Coastal community involvement in LTEM policy development contributed to sustainable marine culture policies (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024). Ecological knowledge was integrated into national policy frameworks as a result of the forest restoration practices (González-Torres et al., 2024). Farmers who were involved in the restoration practices gained greater power in influencing land-use policies (Couix and Gonzalo-Turpin, 2015). In Montana, community participation in river restoration emphasized procedural justice and community ownership in SES (Lauer et al., 2017). In the EU's Mission Ocean and Water initiative, community engagement has increased ocean literacy and created more inclusive policy structures (Whyte et al., 2024). In Rome, local activists got involved in legal advocacy for environmental rights, and scientists utilized the findings from restoration practices to advocate sustainable urban planning (Impedovo et al., 2024). Communities are crucial for long-term sustainability because they have knowledge, have an impact on land-use decisions, and promote inclusive environmental policies.

In a nutshell, communities play a fundamental role in ecosystem regenerative practices through their contributions and shaping the outcomes of these practices across various ecosystems, countries, economies, and cultural systems. The different roles played by community actors in ecosystem regenerative practices are discussed in the next section.

2.4 Community Actor Roles in Ecosystem Regenerative Practices

The analysis of the literature revealed that, while the importance of community engagement is recognized, there is not enough emphasis on the key roles of community actors in ecosystem regenerative practices. Thus, this section presents a synthesis of the reviewed literature to understand the key roles played by community actors in contributing to ecosystem regeneration. Table 4 provides a summary of these key community roles identified through the literature synthesis. Although the roles described do not occur exclusively during the early stages of regenerative practices, they offer valuable insights for understanding how communities contribute to these practices in general.

Table 4. Summary of the Key Community Roles Identified Through the Literature Synthesis

Community Role	Description
Knowledge Holders	Provide Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) to guide these regenerative practices
Initiators	Recognize the urgency of these practices and mobilize others to take action.
Collaborators and Comanagers	Co-design, co-implement, co-manage regenerative projects together with external stakeholders.
Hands-on Contributors	Engage directly in the regenerative practices through physical activities.
Monitors and Stewards	Monitor ecosystem health and ensure long-term sustainability.
Engaged Public and Advocates	Raise awareness, influence policies, and promote public engagement.

Knowledge Holders. Indigenous and local communities who possess Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) through knowledge accrued over generations and first-hand experience in nature, play an important role. Their insights provide valuable information on species behavior, processes of nature, and long-term environmental changes. For example, at Dering-Dibru Saikhowa Elephant Corridor, indigenous communities provided their pioneer knowledge about tree species for forest restoration (Haq et al., 2023). In Mexico at Zicuirán-Infiernillo Biosphere Reserve, local communities provided valuable information in identifying priority areas for forest restoration (González-Torres et al., 2024). The Malgana Aboriginal community integrated ecological knowledge with Western knowledge for seagrass restoration (Sinclair et al., 2024). In Central Brazil, LEK was integrated into conservation and restoration projects (Montenegro et al., 2024). These examples demonstrate the important role played by communities as knowledge holders.

Initiators. Community members act by recognizing the urgency of ecological restoration and facilitating others to engage in these practices. This can be an individual role, a local activist, a group, or a grassroots group. This role is crucial in setting the vision, securing resources, and advocating for community-driven ecosystem regeneration. For example, in the Ghalam Gudeh neighbourhood, local residents established a Neighbourhood Development Centre (NDC) as a hub for regeneration efforts (Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021). In Shark Bay, the Malgana Aboriginal community initiated seagrass restoration

through the ranger program and blended their Ecological Knowledge with scientific knowledge (Sinclair et al., 2024). Likewise, the global network of over 50 restoration sites, the Ecosystem Restoration Communities (ERC) group, engages in community-driven regeneration practices (Sides, 2023). These examples show the important role played by communities as initiators.

Collaboration and Co-management. This happens when communities act together with external stakeholders such as research institutions, NGOs, government agencies, and private entities in ecosystem regenerative practices. Communities, together with the external stakeholders, co-design, co-implement, and co-manage regeneration practices for successful results. For example, in Bangladesh, coastal communities were supported by researchers and donor agencies in seaweed and bivalve farming (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024). In central Savanna restoration, community-led seed networks partnered with scientists to enhance reforestation methods (Montenegro et al., 2024). In Finland, networks, collaborations, and partnerships exist between Maritime Spatial Planning authorities (MSP), regional councils, and the maritime sector stakeholders to co-create a sustainable planning process (Lähde et al., 2024). These examples demonstrate the important role played by communities as collaborators and co-managers.

Hands-on Contributors. Communities act as Hands-on Contributors by directly engaging in implementing regeneration efforts such as tree planting, habitat rehabilitation, land management, and seaweed farming. For example, in Bali, large-scale marine debris beach cleaning projects relied on community support (Koko et al., 2024). In South Africa, local communities actively engaged in restoration practices such as reforestation, afforestation, and reintroduction of native species (Palmer et al., 2022). In South Australia, communities were actively involved in coastal wetland restoration practices (Clarke et al., 2021). These examples show the important role played by communities as hands-on contributors.

Monitors and Stewards. Communities acting as Monitors and Stewards ensure that restored ecosystems remain intact and resilient. Monitoring involves environmental tracking, and stewardship involves long-term cultural and ecological responsibility performed by the communities. For example, in Italy, water and air quality monitoring was done with local participation (Impedovo et al., 2024). In the USA, communities use scientific and indigenous knowledge for monitoring and ecological stewardship (Woelfle-Erskine, 2018). In India, post-reforestation monitoring to track plant survival rates and ecosystem recovery was done

by local communities (Haq et al., 2023). These examples demonstrate the important role played by communities as monitors and stewards.

Engaged Public and Advocates. Communities play an important role as supporters of regenerative practices by raising awareness, lobbying for policy changes, and encouraging public participation. For example, citizen science initiatives in Finland in ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning (Lähde et al., 2024). In Italy, monthly community meetings were held to discuss sustainable management and urban planning policies (Impedovo et al., 2024). These examples show the important role played by communities as engaged public and advocates.

Overall, these roles emphasize various ways in which communities contribute to different stages of ecosystem regenerative practices and also provide a foundation for analyzing and understanding community actor contributions in early-stage regenerative practices in the empirical case of this study. Furthermore, communities contribute to the formation of Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK), which is significantly important in place-based ecosystem regenerative practices.

2.5 Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK)

Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) can be defined as knowledge, practices, and beliefs about ecological connections developed through personal observation and contact with local ecosystems, and shared among local resource users (Charnley et al., 2007, p.15). Further, Davis and Wagner (2003) state that LEK is formed when people develop a very specific and thorough knowledge of their local surroundings and ecological connections based on their experiences, needs, and observations as the outcome of their livelihood dependencies in certain locations. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations defines Local Knowledge (LK) as a collection of information, including people's overall system of concepts, beliefs, and perceptions about their surroundings, which is gained through observations, measurements, solving issues, and verifying new knowledge. This includes a process of creating, storing, applying, and communicating knowledge (FAO, 2004).

Charnley et al. (2007) mentioned that LEK has the potential to become Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) with time. TEK is defined as a collection of knowledge about living beings and their connections with their surrounding and one another that is passed down through generations through cultural transmissions (Berkes, 1999; Joa et al., 2018). In contrast, LEK is gained through personal observations, experiences, and interactions with nature that can be developed over a shorter period, such as knowledge generated in farming or fishing families (Charnley et al., 2007; Emard et al., 2024; Joa et al., 2018). Therefore, as Charnley et al. (2007) stated, LEK potentially converts to TEK with time, portraying the hierarchical relationship between these two components. Some authors use all related terms such as LEK, TEK, and Indigenous Ecological Knowledge (IEK), in synonymous manners, however, the main differences lie in the amount and depth of time during which the knowledge is collected and the historical and cultural context of its development and transmission (Joa et al., 2018).

LEK plays a significant role in ecosystem regenerative practices. First, LEK enhances ecological understanding through detailed and context-specific information about species, ecosystem processes, and environmental changes (Aswani et al., 2020; Karnad, 2022; Joa et al., 2018). In the context of Earth System Models (ESMs), LEK has been used by local participants to identify significant ecosystem processes, including detecting disparities in fire simulations and wildfire predictions in various vegetations that are not presented in scientific models (Emard et al., 2024). Next, LEK provides place-based insights through deep connections to specific locations, which offer spatial and temporal knowledge (Emard et al., 2024; Joa et al., 2018). LEK from artisanal fishers was used for marine spatial planning and participatory mapping because they contain a deep place-based LEK that was formed through their livelihood connection with the environment (Baker and Constant, 2020; Karnad, 2022). Third, LEK provides adaptive knowledge because, with the changing environment, it is important to obtain up-to-date knowledge for regenerative practices (Joa et al., 2018; Leithäuser and Holzacker, 2020). In a fishing village in Vietnam, LEK was co-evolved according to changing environmental conditions by integrating local experiences, which is important for restoration projects (Leithäuser and Holzacker, 2020). Finally, LEK supports long-term environmental stewardship through long-term observations and intergenerational knowledge transmission (Emard et al., 2024; Charnley et al., 2007). LEK often includes cultural norms, spiritual beliefs, and social integration factors that support long-term ecosystem management through the knowledge built over time (Joa et al., 2018).

LEK is formed through direct engagement with the local environment through active observations, hands-on experiences, and trial and error, which may not be similar to scientific methods, however, they are equally rigorous through lived experiences (Hilary and Martin, 1999). Communities develop knowledge of ecological connections, species behavior, and environmental dynamics by engaging in experimental learning over time (Baker and Constant, 2020; Charnley et al., 2007; Emard et al., 2024). Biocentric Work by Albareda and Branzei (2024) describes the cycle of material abduction, where actors iteratively detect biophysical anomalies and build place-based solutions (Albareda and Branzei, 2024). Although not explicitly mentioned, this highlights experimental, trial-and-error processes that align with LEK formation through local community interaction with ecosystems. Furthermore, the relational intercession cycle of biocentric work describes how community actors cooperatively build the infrastructure for new ways of interacting with emergent ecological equilibria (Albareda and Branzei, 2024). This suggests that LEK is dynamically constructed over time through local-material interaction and social cooperation, aligning with the material and relational aspects emphasized in the Biocentric Work framework. In addition, storytelling, shared practices, rituals, languages, and other community-driven practices are important for the transmission of LEK (Toner et al., 2023). When LEK gets integrated with new information from external sources such as media, science, NGOs, or government agents, it forms hybrid knowledge systems (Joa et al., 2018). Therefore, the collaboration between local communities and scientists can lead to hybrid knowledge formation where local observations and experiences are connected with scientific methods (Emard et al., 2024; Ruddle and Davis, 2011).

LEK plays a fundamental role in the formation of regenerative business models because it requires critical place-based ecological understanding (Rahman et al., 2024). It requires a continuous process of seeking, acquiring, and applying place-based ecological insights to shape the business strategies to enhance the environment. LEK offers an understanding of the local ecosystems, supports identifying regenerative practices tailored for specific locations, development of place-based solutions, guides value creation to align with nature regeneration, and supports integrating these values into the core of the business model (Rahman et al., 2024). These deep connections formed through LEK creations allow business models to move beyond merely being sustainable to actively contribute to the regeneration of SES.

Overall, LEK provides an important foundation for communities to meaningfully engage in ecosystem regenerative practices through adaptive, place-based, experimental practices while laying the foundation for future businesses to align with changing environmental conditions.

2.6 Community Contributions Towards Regenerative Business Approaches

This section outlines the synthesis of the literature reviewed to showcase diverse business approaches that emerge through community contributions to ecosystem regenerative practices. These models integrate economic benefits, environmental restoration and enhancement of ecological regeneration, and social equity and resilience, highlighting the SES embeddedness. The identified business approaches and models through the literature synthesis include regenerative farming and aquaculture, value-added processing, conservation-based tourism, and employment opportunities.

Regenerative Farming and Aquaculture. This is the most common business model emerging from community-driven regenerative practices. In Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh, coastal fishers and farmers participated in Low Trophic Extractive Mariculture (LTEM), by cultivating seaweed and bivalves and gained economic benefits (earned \$50–\$650 per season, depending on farm size), highlighting the economic potential of regenerative ocean farming (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024). The EU Mission in Ocean and Water community-driven business models for regenerative ocean farming were developed, such as the C-FAARER project (Kapletia et al., 2023; Whyte et al., 2024). In Central Brazil, indigenous communities and small landholders were involved in native seed collection and commercialization through several networks (Montenegro et al., 2024). Community seed collectors earn about USD 1306 – USD 8146 annual income; thus, these models showcase how community-based supply chains are driven by local knowledge and participation (Montenegro et al., 2024). The Ecosystem Restoration Communities (ERC) projects aim to create sustainable business models for communities, integrating agroforestry, permaculture farming, and ecotourism (Sides, 2023). The final aim is to make each community financially sustainable through these regenerative business models (Sides, 2023).

Ecotourism and Nature-based Enterprises. These are new business approaches that apply nature regeneration as an incentive for economic growth. Some indigenous communities in

the United States have integrated ecotourism and buffalo ranching to create revenue while encouraging sustainable tourism and animal protection (Zytkoskee et al., 2024). Similar to this, ecotourism businesses have been proposed for elephant corridor restoration projects in India, enabling local communities to earn money while preserving animal habitat connectivity (Haq et al., 2023). Co-creation in marine spatial planning has integrated tourist sector participation in sustainable tourism in Finland (Lähde et al., 2024). These cases illustrate how responsible tourism models can be promoted by establishing a balance between economic development and regeneration.

Job Creation. Further, these practices result in the creation of jobs in these fields. For example, in Shark Bay, indigenous communities were employed for seagrass restoration practices and monitoring activities (Sinclair et al., 2024). In the Loess Plateau, jobs were created in forestry-related practices such as planting trees and land restoration (Qu et al., 2017). In India, participants were paid a daily wage for their involvement in the restoration practices (Haq et al., 2023). This demonstrates how, especially in indigenous conservation projects, environmental regeneration practices may lead to employment opportunities. Instead of being seen as a strictly volunteer or conservation-driven activity, these cases demonstrate how environmental regeneration may lead to structured employment.

Value Added Processing and Product Development. Some communities engage in transitioning raw materials collected through these regenerative practices to value-added product development in order to gain commercial value. Bangladesh coastal communities use seaweeds cultivated to manufacture food, fertilizer, and bio-based materials-related products. Further, they export these products to India, Korea, China, Singapore, and Chile. This shows how regenerative ocean farming leads to emerging business models (Ahmed et al., 2022). In Bali, Indonesia, hypothetical community-driven ecosystem regeneration practices have explored waste recycling and upcycling initiatives by converting marine debris into commercial products (Koko et al., 2024). These cases demonstrate how community-driven regenerative practices may lead to innovative product-based enterprises.

Table 5. Summary of Regenerative Business Approaches Identified Through the Literature Synthesis

Business Approach	Community Contribution
Regenerative Farming and Aquaculture	Cultivating, Harvesting, Local Supply Chain Coordination

Ecotourism and Nature-based Enterprises	Habitat Restoration, Promoting Sustainable Tourism
Job Creation	Participating in Ecosystem Restoration and Regeneration as Paid Work
Value Added Processing and Product Development	Producing and Exporting Value Added Eco-Products from Local Resources

Table 5 summarises the business approaches that emerge through community contribution to ecosystem regenerative practices. This literature synthesis shows that community contributions not only initiate regenerative practices but also contribute to the creation of diverse, locally rooted business approaches through these ecosystem regenerative practices.

2.7 Conceptual Lens of the Study

The literature reviewed in this study focuses on community involvement in general in ecosystem regenerative practices without mentioning the exact phase of the process. In contrast, this study explicitly focuses on the early-stage phase where community actors become core to the foundations for ecosystem regenerative practices and regenerative business model emergence. Ecosystem regenerative practices in the context of the community begin with the motivations of actors' social intentions, actions, and values embedded in the local communities living in these ecosystems.

Community actors involved in early-stage ecosystem regeneration actively contribute within various roles (eg, Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Clarke et al., 2021; González-Torres et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2023; Impedovo et al., 2024; Koko et al., 2024; Lähde et al., 2024; Montenegro et al., 2024; Palmer et al., 2022; Sides, 2023, Sinclair et al., 2024; Woelfle-Erskine, 2018). This study positions early-stage ecosystem regeneration as deeply rooted in the community, where it is understood through the lens of Community Actor Roles and the formation of Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK). These two aspects lay the foundation for the initiation of ecosystem regenerative practices and the future regenerative business models.

The synthesis of the selected literature identified six key community roles in ecosystem regenerative practices as Knowledge Holders, Initiators, Collaborators and Co-managers,

Hands-on Contributors, Monitors and Stewards, and Engaged Public and Advocates (See Table 4). Understanding these roles provides a conceptual lens to analyze the community actor roles in the case study of this research. This creates the first pillar of the conceptual lens.

LEK is developed through personal observation and contact with local ecosystems. People develop specific and thorough knowledge of their local surroundings and ecological connections based on their experiences, needs, and observations as the outcome of their livelihood dependencies in certain locations (Charnley et al., 2007; Davis and Wagner, 2003). It is important to understand LEK to analyze the knowledge formation aspect in the case study at its early development stage. Therefore, this serves as the second pillar of the conceptual lens.

Figure 4. Conceptual Lens of the Study (Author Generated)

Although the two conceptual pillars identified are not formalized theories, they serve as the core conceptual lens for this study. *Community actor roles and LEK* together offer a structured way to understand community contribution for the initiation of ecosystem regenerative practices, and knowledge is built for broader community engagement and regenerative business model emergence (Figure 4).

According to the conceptual lens, community actors enable the initiation of regenerative practices through various roles, and then LEK is formed by these community actors to create broader community engagement and conditions for regenerative business models. This conceptual lens, proposed by the researcher through the literature synthesis, guides the empirical data analysis in the following sections.

3 Research Design and Methods

This chapter describes the research design and methods of this study. It includes the assumed research philosophy, case description, data collection, sampling, and analysis methods, followed by the reliability and validity considerations of this research.

According to Creswell (2009) and Aityan (2022), Research can be defined as a systematic process with a clear research problem and a correct methodological approach in order to understand problems, address research gaps, and provide solutions. Accordingly, this research project began with the initial engagement with the case study organization through a virtual meeting with the Aktion Österbotten. This initial interaction supported identifying and realizing that the research should focus on community participation in regenerative practices, which resulted in defining the research focus of this study. Figure 5 summarizes the phases of this research process.

Figure 5. Phases of the Research Process (Author Generated)

After defining the research focus, an initial review of the literature was conducted adopting a Systematic Literature Review methodology for the screening and selection of articles to guarantee a structured, transparent, and comprehensive review of existing literature on community involvement in ecosystem regenerative and restorative practices (Kraus et al.,

2020; Tranfield et al., 2003). Since the topic of Regeneration is a novel, emerging research area in the organizational and business management field, this review included literature from multiple fields such as social sciences, economics, finance, decision sciences, psychology, and planetary sciences. The initial screening and selection processes are further described using visuals in Appendices (See Appendix 1). Further, descriptive analysis conducted on this set of initially selected papers is presented from Appendix 2 – Appendix 5, including key publication trends, journal distribution, academic rigor, publication timeline, theoretical and conceptual foundations, and geographical and ecosystem distribution. Initially, the study focused on the Biocentric Framework by Albareda and Branzei (2024) as the theoretical lens, and the literature was analysed using this lens (Appendix 6).

In the meantime, participation in a Duck Mussel Business Model Workshop and a Tasting Event provided valuable deeper contextual understandings of the case and supported in identifying relevant community actors and collecting field observational data for the study.

Next, the research methodology was formulated, defining this study as a single case study that focuses extensively on one phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2016). Semi-structured interviews were planned, and relevant questions were formulated depending on the contribution of each community actor interviewed. After conducting the interviews, they were analyzed according to the Gioia Method (Gioia et al., 2013) using NVivo for the coding process. This process resulted in identifying four main aggregated dimensions with one cross-cutting theme.

After the empirical data analysis, it became evident that Biocentric Work had not fully emerged in this case study. However, this led to an interesting phenomenon where it showed early-stage phases driven by community actors in initiating ecosystem regenerative practices. Therefore, the conceptual lens of the study was changed to understand the contribution of community actors in initiating these practices, forming Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK), and laying the foundations for future regenerative business models, which better reflect the real dynamics in this case.

To better explain these empirical findings, additional articles were added to the literature review, and a more comprehensive literature review was carried out. A literature review is a critical, evidence-based evaluation of existing knowledge on a topic (Winchester and Salji,

2016). Therefore, it synthesizes current literature, going beyond simply listing and summarizing them, which results in identifying gaps in the field (Creswell, 2009; Winchester and Salji, 2016). After identifying the research gap, the research question was formulated.

Using the four main aggregated dimensions identified through the Gioia analysis method, an empirical model was developed to answer the research question of this study. The findings were interpreted, also highlighting theoretical contributions, practical implications, and suggestions for future research as the final phase of the study.

3.1 Research Philosophy

The way the researcher views the world is explained by the research philosophy, describing how knowledge is perceived, constructed, and interpreted in the study (Creswell and Clark, 2018; Saunders et al., 2016). This includes key assumptions about human knowledge (epistemological assumptions), realities (ontological assumptions), the influence of the researcher's values on the process (axiological assumptions), and the methods used in the study (methodology) (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Saunders et al., 2016). These assumptions will be applied in research through paradigms or interpretive frameworks (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008; Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

This study adopts a *constructivist ontological view*, assuming that reality is not fixed or objective but rather created through social interactions, cultural experiences, and contextual interpretation (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). This view explains different realities created by complex and organized patterns through ongoing processes (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). In this study, ecosystem regeneration is seen as a locally and socially defined evolving process by community actors through their engagement, experience, and place-based knowledge formation, not as a fixed process.

Further, the *epistemological stance* of this study is *interpretivism*, where knowledge is seen as co-constructed through social processes created by narratives, perceptions, and interpretations (Saunders et al., 2016). This view focuses on understanding how people make sense of their world through experiences rather than uncovering universal laws (Saunders et al., 2016). In this study, knowledge of ecosystem regenerative practices emerges through the

narratives, perceptions, and interactions of the participants, which are interpreted through the researcher's positional lens.

Figure 6. Summary of Research Philosophy (Author Generated)

Accordingly, the adapted methodological approach of this study is a single case study design, which aligns with the philosophical positioning and data collection methods of interviews and field observations.

3.2 Research Methodology

This research is a qualitative study, and as explained by Creswell (2009), these types of studies explore and understand the meaning that individuals or groups assign to a social or human problem. This study adopted *Abductive* reasoning, which is a combination of inductive and deductive approaches (Suddaby, 2006). This study moved back and forth between theory and data, where it began with an initial theoretical lens of Biocentric Work (Albareda and Branzei, 2024) and then, with surprising empirical findings it led to a shift in focus to a conceptual lens of community actor and LEK formation (Saunders et al., 2016; Suddaby, 2006; Van Maanen et al., 2007).

The methodological strategy of this study is a *single case study*. A case study is an empirical investigation that analyzes a current phenomenon (the 'case') within its real-life environment, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not easily distinguished (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015; Yin, 2014). Further, this is a single case study, as defined by Yin (2009) and O'Gorman and MacIntosh (2015), to deeply explore a single bounded system that is an individual, group, or organization. This study is an exploratory type of single case study due to the novelty of the context and the exploratory

nature of the research question, which was formulated after data analysis was completed (O’Gorman and MacIntosh, 2015).

The emerging regenerative ocean farming initiative in Ostrobothnia, Finland, was selected as the case study because of its uniqueness, relevance, and potential to generate unexplored conceptual insights in the field. The case is geographically bounded in the coastal region of Ostrobothnia, and data collection was done from late 2024 to the beginning of 2025. The aim was to understand the contributions of different community actors involved in the initiative rather than studying a single organization.

The role of the researcher was active and reflexive during the process as she participated in events and engaged with community actors to collect observational data to supplement the interview data, rather than being a detached spectator (Dodgson, 2019).

3.3 Case Description

The case study focuses on community-driven regenerative ocean farming initiated in the coastal region of Ostrobothnia in Finland. This initiative aims to explore how food can be produced in the ocean in a regenerative manner, focusing on different species. This study exclusively focuses on the extension of a mussel species named the Duck Mussels (*Anodonta anatina*). Duck Mussel is a freshwater species that has never been included as a food before. The goal is to extend the duck mussels in low salinity water of Ostrobothnia with two main targets: to reduce the amount of nutrients of the water solving algae blooms in the coastal areas, and as a mussel species that is a healthy protein source which can be used by local communities as new locally sourced food. This potentially lays the foundations for the emergence of new regenerative business models.

These efforts began two years ago, initiated by a core team of actors from Aktion Österbotten, a Local Action Group (LAG) and Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) that spans across 13 municipalities in Ostrobothnia (Aktion Österbotten, 2024). This project is in an early development phase where initial experimentations, ecological knowledge formation, and exploration of novel food systems are done by several local community actors. They are the leading organization in this initiative in Finland, and also the country

facilitators of Finland for European Union projects on regenerative ocean farming: Cool Blue (Horizon) and Cool Blue Baltic (EMFAF).

Duck mussel regenerative ocean farming in Ostrobothnia is currently non-commercial as it is not yet commercialized or even extended as a main practice. But the goal of the key actors of this project is to engage local communities with a goal of commercialization in the future. The project has two circles of actors that belong to the local communities. First, it is mainly driven by the key actors and experts of Aktion Österbotten in collaboration with other community actors such as local chefs, fishermen, and researchers. Second, they aim to extend and implement local community engagement this spring and summer season to engage and co-create solutions with land and water owners. As of now, duck mussels are not legalized as a novel food, but pilot and experimental activities are being carried out to generate Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK), raise community awareness, and explore potential future value chains. These community actors contribute at various levels, spanning from initiation and designing the regenerative vision to experimenting and promoting these activities.

This case was selected due to its theoretical and exploratory potential and novelty, where ecosystem regenerative initiatives are in their early stages of formation. This allows the researcher to explore and understand the very beginning of how ecosystem regeneration is envisioned, initiated, and organized at the community level. Further, this case offers insights into understanding the intersection of cultural values, ecological intentions, and business thinking, aligning with the research question of this study: *How do community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices, and how do their contributions lay the foundation for regenerative business models?* A summary of key characteristics of the case study is provided in Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of Case Study Context

Element	Description
Case Study Title	Community Driven Regenerative Ocean Farming
Geographical Scope	Coastal Region of Ostrobothnia, Finland
Ecosystem	Marine and coastal ecosystems of Ostrobothnia Coastal Region
Regenerative Practice	Ocean Regeneration through different species and explore sustainable food systems

Focus Species of this Study	Duck Mussels (<i>Anodonta anatina</i>)
Development Stage	Early Stage, Exploratory, Pre-commercial
Community Actors	First Circle: Members of Aktion Österbotten, Local Chef, Fishermen, and Researchers Second Circle: Land and Water Owners, Activists and Local Community Members

3.4 Data Collection Methods

This study used two primary data collection methods, namely, *semi-structured interviews* and *observer-as-participant observations*, with supplementary data collected through meetings and discussions. According to Saunders et al. (2016), semi-structured interviews are designed with a list of questions under themes, however, these may vary according to the interview. As an observer-as-participant, the main focus is on observation over participation, however, there are occasional informal interactions with the participants where the researcher's identity and purpose are clearly communicated (Saunders et al., 2016).

A total of seven semi-structured interviews were conducted with different community actors involved in various roles within this early stage of the regenerative ocean farming practice. Interviews were tailored to reflect each interviewee's specific role. All interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams in English. Interview durations ranged from approximately 60 to 90 minutes. All interviews were recorded and automatically transcribed via Microsoft Teams with the consent of the interviewee. Refer to Appendix 8 – Appendix 12 for the interview questions designed depending on each actor's role.

The researcher also participated in observer-as-participant observations by attending two key community events, a duck mussel-tasting event and a stakeholder workshop on regenerative business models. The tasting event was hosted at a local restaurant and featured a chef who prepared duck mussels in different culinary methods for the invited guests. The business model workshop was facilitated by two business researchers and was designed to provide the members of Aktion Österbotten with a better understanding of the business and commercialization aspects of regenerative ocean farming.

In addition to the above, the researcher engaged in informal discussions and virtual meetings that enriched her understanding of this case. One unrecorded yet insightful discussion with the Executive Director of Aktion Österbotten offered valuable insights into the early-stage phase of this initiative. Further, three initial virtual meetings were held via Microsoft Teams with members of Aktion Österbotten to clarify and understand this initiative, which helped to identify relevant actors and shape the focus of the research.

Table 7. Summary of the Data Collected

Data Type	Participant(s)	Date	Location/Mode
Meeting	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	11.11.2024	Microsoft Teams
Meeting	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	18.11.2024	Microsoft Teams
Interview 1	Fisheries Leader Advisor of Aktion Österbotten	25.11.2024	Microsoft Teams
Meeting	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	16.12.2024	Microsoft Teams
4 hours Workshop (Observation)	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	16.1.2025	Aktion Österbotten Office
Tasting Event (Observation)	Organized by members Aktion Österbotten. 20 participants: researchers, chef, journalists, fishermen, aquaculture entrepreneurs	16.1.2025	Local Restaurant
Field Work Meeting (Discussion)	Executive Director of Aktion Österbotten	17.1.2025	Personal Setting (in-person)
Interview 2	Biologist Researcher	10.2.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 3	Project Manager of Aktion Österbotten	17.2.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 4	Fisheries Leader Advisor of Aktion Österbotten	26.2.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 5	Owner and chef of the Local Restaurant	4.3.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 6	Fishermen A	4.3.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 7	Fishermen B	10.3.2025	Microsoft Teams

Table 7 provides a detailed summary of the data collection activities. This diverse set of data collection methods allowed for a thorough and continuing understanding of the case and was supported by various views and sources to enrich the study.

3.5 Sampling Strategy

Initially, the researcher employed the *Purposeful Sampling* strategy, which is a common strategy used in qualitative research (Creswell, 2013). Patton (2015) defines this strategy as choosing cases to examine that are rich in information and that will provide insight into the research topic by their very nature and content. The logic and power of purposeful sampling are that the selected cases are rich in information for an in-depth study (Creswell, 2013; Patton, 2015), thus the Executive Director, Fisheries Leader Advisor, and Project Manager of Aktion Österbotten responsible for this initiative were selected to gain a rich, contextual understanding of how community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices.

Table 8. Overview of Interview Participants

Participant Role	Community Context	Sampling Method
Executive Director	Member of Aktion Österbotten	Purposeful
Fisheries Leader Advisor	Member of Aktion Österbotten	Purposeful
Project Manager	Member of Aktion Österbotten	Purposeful
Biologist Researcher	External Academic Collaborator	Snowball
Local Chef	Local Restaurant	Snowball
Fisherman A	Local Community	Snowball
Fisherman B	Local Community	Snowball

This was followed by *Snowball Sampling*, meaning initial participants referred the researcher to other suitable participants for the study (Creswell, 2013; Patton, 2015). In this study, members from Aktion Österbotten introduced the researcher to other external community actors involved in the initiative, such as two fishermen who supported early-stage experimentation, a local chef who hosted the public tasting event, and a biologist researcher supporting knowledge-building and hatchery development in this project. The goal was to gain an in-depth understanding of this case, which was achieved through these sampling strategies. Participant roles identified in Table 8 will be used to identify the quotations in the Findings Chapter (Chapter 4).

3.6 Data Analysis

The *Gioia Method* was utilized in this study as the empirical data analysis method. The process of the data analysis of this study is demonstrated in Figure 7. The Gioia Method is a systematic inductive method of conceptual development that prioritizes maintaining informants' voices through first-order codes while allowing theoretical abstraction through second-order themes and aggregate dimensions (Gioia et al., 2013). This approach is suitable for this study as the goal is to uncover new concepts and grounded theoretical insights using the exploratory single-case study (Gioia, 2021). To facilitate the coding process, NVivo 14 was used to organize, explore, and code the empirical data collected. As Creswell (2013) mentioned, NVivo is an effective tool for managing, shaping, and analyzing qualitative data.

Figure 7. Data Analysis Process (Author Generated)

First, the seven interview transcripts obtained via Microsoft Teams were manually cleaned by removing unnecessary conversational parts such as greetings, endings, and small talk. Then these cleaned transcripts were uploaded to NVivo to create the first-order concepts.

First-order concepts are the initial data codes that are created, which are close to the interviewees' own language in order to capture their lived experience without any interpretations (Gioia et al., 2013). This step, which is also called open coding, often creates

a larger number of diverse sets of codes (Gioia et al., 2013). In this study, approximately 470 first-order concepts were created in this initial step (Appendix 7).

Figure 8. Gioia Data Structure Visual (Author Generated)

The next step was to create the second-order themes according to the Gioia method. Second-order themes are defined as researcher-centric concepts that emerge when further analysis is done to identify theoretical patterns, relationships, and explanations (Gioia et al., 2013). This process was done by comparing and grouping similar first-order concepts into themes and labeling them with abstract phrasal descriptions to reflect the core meaning of the grouped concepts (Gioia et al., 2013). This step resulted in 15 second-order themes for this study

(Appendix 7), developed to answer the central question “What’s going on here?” (Gioia et al., 2013).

The final step was identifying the aggregated dimensions, as explained by Gioia et al. (2013), which are overarching theoretical categories that emerge through the further analysis of the second-order themes created in order to discover deeper structural patterns in the data. In this step, the researcher grouped the 15 second-order themes under four higher-level Aggregated Dimensions as Strategic Foundations for Regenerative Practice, Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) Formation, Motivations, Mechanisms, and Pathways for Community Engagement, and Pathways for the Emergence of Regenerative Business Models. This final step of data structuring supported the researcher in synthesizing the emerging concepts into a clear framework by organizing first-order concepts, second-order themes, and aggregated dimensions into a layered hierarchical data structure visual (Figure 8).

Figure 9. Cross-Cutting Theme of Barriers, Tensions, and Structural Limitations (Author Generated)

However, in addition to the four distinct aggregated dimensions derived through the Gioia method, one additional theme emerged repeatedly across the dataset, listing the challenges and limitations that impact every aggregated dimension identified (Appendix 7). Therefore, this theme cuts across multiple dimensions from strategic initiation to business model emergence. Following Kalfa et al. (2021) and Jiménez-Partearroyo et al. (2024), who incorporated cross-cutting themes to capture overarching dynamics such as cultural or

structural aspects in their Gioia analysis, this study introduces a similar theme to understand the structural and contextual challenges that appeared in the empirical data. Aligning with the flexible and iterative nature of the Gioia method (Gioia et al., 2013), this cross-cutting theme of Barriers, Tensions, and Structural Limitations was introduced to provide theoretical clarity around the limitations of this regenerative practice at this early stage (Figure 9).

3.7 Validity, Reliability, and Generalizability of the Study

This study adopted a rigorous qualitative research process in order to guarantee the reliability, validity, and generalizability of the study. To ensure qualitative validity, the researcher must check the accuracy of the findings by utilizing suitable procedures (Gibbs, 2007). To ensure qualitative reliability, the researcher must ensure consistency and dependability of the research process (Gibbs, 2007).

To ensure the study's *validity* by enhancing the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings, different methods and techniques were utilized as introduced by Creswell (2009) and Saunders et al. (2016). Data triangulation was ensured by using more than one source of data collection methods, including semi-structured interviews, observer-as-participant observations, virtual meetings, and in-person discussions. Member Reflections were conducted in a feasible manner, where key interpretations and themes were discussed with the individuals from the regional development organization. Rich and thick descriptions were provided to convey the case and findings, which allows the readers an in-depth understanding of the study. To avoid researcher bias, the researcher took active steps to openly communicate her prior involvement in this case. Reflexive notes were written during data collection and analysis to understand any personal feelings or assumptions in order to convey participants' voices and experiences without being clouded by personal views. Negative evidence, such as barriers, tensions, and structural limitations, was included as a cross-cutting theme to enhance the analytical honesty and complexity of the findings.

To ensure the study's *reliability* by enhancing consistency in data handling, multiple strategies were used as described in Creswell (2009) and Saunders et al. (2016). First, all interview transcripts were manually checked by the researcher to ensure the accuracy of the participants' voices. The coding process was carefully documented, and the software NVivo 14 was used to organize and maintain the codes. The Gioia method was followed for a

systematic analysis of the findings following the steps of first-order concepts, second-order themes, and aggregated dimensions. Finally, the data structures were discussed with the thesis supervisors to enhance the reliability through reflective feedback.

In the context of generalizability, this single case study does not aim for statistical generalization but rather offers analytical insights that may be transferable to similar community-led regenerative initiatives in other contexts (Yin, 2009).

4 Findings

This chapter presents the empirical findings from the data collected. The conceptual lens of this study was built around two pillars that were derived through the literature synthesis: community actor roles and LEK formation, which together were expected to support early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and business model emergence (See Figure 4). This conceptual lens laid the foundation to analyze the empirical data. However, the data analysis using the Gioia method revealed a more dynamic and interrelated set of processes to understand how communities contribute to ecosystem regeneration in practice. Figure 10 presents the four aggregated dimensions identified through the Gioia analysis.

Figure 10. Process Model of Community Engagement in Regenerative Ocean Farming Derived Through the Gioia Analysis (Author Generated)

The findings are introduced following these four aggregated dimensions, under each second-order theme, using direct quotes from interviewees and other observational data when applicable to support and contextualize each dimension. These four dimensions lay the foundation for building a process model of community engagement in regenerative ocean farming. This process model illustrates that community actors are not merely engaged in predefined roles, but rather strategically initiate, create LEK, foster community engagement, and shape future business approaches to collectively support ecosystem regenerative

practices. This chapter presents the process model of community co-creation for ecosystem regeneration practices and regenerative business model emergence. In addition, the final section discusses the cross-cutting theme, explaining the key barriers and tensions that emerged across the process.

4.1 Strategic Foundations for Regenerative Practice

The first dimension presents the initiation and strategic foundations laid for the early development of regenerative ocean farming in Ostrobothnia, Finland. At the core of this effort were members from the Aktion Österbotten organization, and they played a key role in setting the vision, securing funding, discovering network platforms, coordinating stakeholder engagement, designing early-stage experimentations, and guiding long-term planning. Data showcases how these actions laid the groundwork for knowledge development, community engagement and participation, and potential regenerative business emergence.

Strategic Vision and Leadership. Key actors of Aktion Österbotten expressed their vision for regenerative ocean farming, clearly stating that their dual vision is to produce food in a regenerative way from the ocean while cleaning the water.

“I want to produce food and clean the water. I want to produce food in a way that cleans the water; that’s what I want to do. And that’s also maybe why I’m so interested in the duck mussel because I see that as food....” - Fisheries Leader Advisor

Their goal was not to replicate a system from another location but to create a new system that suits their region in Finland because of the low-salinity water conditions in the coastal region of Ostrobothnia. Therefore, they first looked at different species that can survive in low-salinity water, which can be used as a food source.

“When we started, we questioned, what does the regenerative ocean farming look like in Finland with our low salinity....so we have looked at candidate species that we think could thrive well in our waters, that are edible or used for other purposes in specific ways....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

In addition, their long-term goal is to develop the right production model for duck mussels so they can be used both for cleaning water and as food.

“The long-term goal is to find the production model for these duck mussels, so we could reproduce them and grow them in the most productive environments....so they can be produced on small scales anywhere and on a big scale, where it's best to produce big scale. That's our goal....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

They mention that this approach is a blend of innovation with a strong commitment to learning. They position this effort as a broader shift towards regeneration, and they acknowledge that they are engaging in the initial phases of this bigger outcome.

“I'm quite innovative and try to because this is a new thing....I educate myself all the time....I'm a practitioner, so I want to find a solution, and now I think that this is worth testing....We have started a movement, but we have a long way to go because this is the first step.” – Project Manager

These findings show the strategic visioning and leadership of the key community actors involved in this initiative.

Network and Strategic Collaborative Efforts. They also applied and named Finland a member of a European Union Initiative named Cool Blue Future. This platform brought together members from different EU countries, creating a formal international networking platform.

“So, we got in this cool blue project. And it's actually two projects. It's Cool Blue that started in Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, and Estonia. And then after that, started the Cool Blue Baltic project, which is the same countries, plus the countries on the eastern part of the Baltic Sea....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Further, they plan on creating a national-level network in the future in order to bring together all stakeholders engaged in these related ocean regeneration practices in Finland. They recognize that it is crucial to collaborate and create a network because this is not something that can be done alone, and they need to build knowledge around this. Further, they have recognized that collaborations with experts are needed, especially in the legal aspects, such as novel food processes. This highlights the need for collaboration to move forward with this initiative.

“....we can't move this elephant by ourselves. We have to connect....” – Project Manager

“Nobody knows so much so it is really important that we build a better network around this topic....if we in a real way build some kind of network....a hub for

the development of regenerative aquaculture in Finland....we engage the research people, project people, organizations, fishermen, growers and people that are really getting their feet dirty. So, if we can engage all of them and get to discuss....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“We need someone who has and takes the time to really get into this. To get more information and evaluate. Investigate and evaluate to see what the best way is to go forward. So, I think we need help from somebody who knows legislation....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Although the initiation of the project was done by the members of Aktion Österbotten, they engaged several external actors from the community, such as a local chef and fishermen. These actors portrayed them as pioneers and ambassadors of this project, and also actively contributed to early experimentation and community engagement activities.

“It’s a little bit of being an ambassador at this time to try to get any people interested....” – Local Chef

“Few pioneers start something new, and then if they make it, then there are many who will follow...it’s the pioneering that is always exciting....I think everybody has some kind of a sense that they want to be like an explorer in some sense, and it’s very interesting to be doing something not many people or no one has done before....in that sense, I think it’s very rewarding....” – Fisherman B

Production Infrastructure and Strategic Planning. In the early stages, actors recognized that there was a need for a hatchery and did experiments with local as well as lab-based solutions for duck mussel reproduction. Actors did not intend to rely only on lab-based hatcheries but also experimented with other local options. Members of Aktion Österbotten are planning to experiment with natural locations to create a natural hatchery while the biologist researcher is working on lab-based options.

*“....we can’t only rely on....I’m not so sure when we’re going to get them....so he wanted us to think about how to develop some hatchery locally....We have started to look at the places where they have taken gravel before. So, we have a lot of big ponds in the forest, and if we can find a good one and put....There will be a nursery there in the middle of the forest where there is clean water....”
- Project Manager*

“We would like to try a natural pond and also in gauges with a bottom of sand or silt in the bottom and so on....This is more natural, like reproduction, and succeed with that. When we try different methods, something will work.” - Fisheries Leader Advisor

“I have a PhD student who is developing a method....will be developing on a Petri dish without the fish....And cell culture medium. So, you could skip the fish because it’s a bit complicated to keep the fish there....” – Biologist Researcher

This project is still in the initiation phase as a pilot project, but members from Aktion Österbotten are planning to move this project to a successful outcome. They have planned what needs to be done in the spring and summer, and what equipment needs to be built for the operations.

“....This is more like a testing pilot project....” – Fisherman A

“....what we have done mostly in the last month is that we have discussed and planned what kind of work and what we will do for the spring and summer, and what kind of equipment we have to build” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Testing, Site Selection, and Experimental Foundations. Further, they are experimenting to find suitable places and environmental conditions for the duck mussels. Early trials were done and are also planned to be carried out in the future to determine these factors and collect knowledge and data. Also, trials are done for experimenting with cage designs, cage placements, and prototyping. There is a crucial need for conducting initial experiments because of the novelty and the early-stage phase of this practice. At this phase, according to the community actors, a lot is not known, and various kinds of explorations must be carried out to form this initial local ecological knowledge.

“We don’t really know the....It’s around 30 meters in depth, and we don’t really know what’s best. Is it a good place at the bottom or in the middle? Or is it like 5/10/15 meters? And how much sunlight and what other factors are needed? So, I think there is quite a lot to investigate that we don’t know. So, I think, for this year it’s better to try to find out a little bit about what depth and optimal conditions are needed for mussel growth....” – Fisherman B

“So last Thursday, we tried to figure out different kinds of ways. We did different kinds of drawings, and so I think we started a new process...we have been sitting together discussing what kind of cages we need....This spring we both will be developing something....” – Project Manager

Overall, these actions show how community actors contribute to the strategic initiation of regenerative ocean farming through vision-setting, strategic planning, practical experimentation, and strategic collaboration, which lay the foundation for Local Ecological

Knowledge (LEK) generation, broader community engagement, and future regenerative business model development.

4.2 Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) Formation

The second aggregated dimension identified is Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) Formation. As seen in the strategic foundation phase, there is an urgent need to create place-based ecological knowledge before engaging broader communities or developing business models. Relevant LEK related to the new species and the Baltic Sea marine ecosystem needs to be formed. In this early stage of the project, key community actors are collaboratively building LEK through hands-on experimentation, environmental observations, and sensory learning. This will be extended to a second circle of community-based actors in the next spring and summer season for further experimentation.

Building Biological and Reproductive Knowledge of Duck Mussels. Initiators and collaborators are trying to understand the growth and reproductive cycle of duck mussels in nature because of the current knowledge gaps. They are trying to build this LEK around the biology of the duck mussel. During the interviews, they explained the knowledge they have built so far.

“They are small mussels, but they are really small, like two. And from that, they then grow. During the next summer, they will grow between one and two centimeters. So, then you can see after one year....and after three years, they can grow up to four or five centimeters. So, in good conditions and environments, they can be of edible size in three years.” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“Yeah, because the mussels are fertilized in the autumn. And then the baby mussels are living inside the female mussel....they start coming out in the winter....Until May, and then they start to dip down and then go under the sand and live there for some time, and then they go up and start to filter, and they are around one centimeter in size around autumn.” – Project Manager

Building Environmental and Ecosystem Services Knowledge of Duck Mussels. Further, these experiments and learning processes resulted in forming practicalities of duck mussels, such as observing the water filtration ability, biodiversity, and ecosystem enhancement insights. According to the biologist researcher, the filtering process of duck mussels results

in removing harmful bacteria from the water, which is beneficial for the fish, and this also results in enhanced biodiversity and ecosystems.

“This duck mussel, for example, when it’s filtering, it’s also filtering bacteria that are harmful to fish and bacteria that are very harmful to fish farming....The presence of duck mussels decreases the density of these bacteria and clean water statistically significantly.” – Biologist Researcher

“....that’s a very good food for these invertebrate insect larvae and things like this come there and so they prepare food for fish, so they can, like, contribute to the fish like trout populations....” – Biologist Researcher

The project manager explained how she plans on building a pond in a ditch to put duck mussels and different plants to check the water quality improvement.

“....we have been discussing if we could do a pond on this ditch so we can put different kinds of plants there, and also mussels, and then we can look at the water quality before and after of this pond.” – Project Manager

Further, it was mentioned that she is going to experiment with duck mussels in a graveyard and that it is really interesting to see the results.

“It’s a little bit like high flying, but when I see that I have a possibility to get something done now with the graveyard, it’s really interesting to test with that....” – Project Manager

Building Sensory and Culinary Knowledge of Duck Mussels. In addition to these experiments, actors create knowledge through the culinary exploration of duck mussels. Experiments were done with the local chef to check the taste, texture, and means of cooking. The chef and fisherman B mentioned that the taste of the duck mussels depends on where they lived before they are cooked, so they will taste exactly like the waters they lived in.

“They can be there as long as they are not at the bottom. They need to be lifted up, I just believe that they are going to taste the same, that the water is tasting where they live, but they need to be lifted up a little bit because otherwise, they are going to taste like mud.” – Local Chef

“....when you have something in the sea, of course, there’s a little bit more like a sea or ocean flavor in it....” – Fisherman B

Fisheries Leader Advisor mentioned that they tested duck mussels in a restaurant with invited guests and also at public events, engaging the public and children, and they plan on testing more in the future.

“So, we have tested them with guests in a restaurant, and we will test more....and we have also had public demonstrations and gave duck mussels to the public and to children to try...” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

The researcher attended one of the tasting event held at a local restaurant where the chef prepared the mussels, and a few guests were invited to taste them. The event offered experiential feedback about the taste and texture, and also revealed the curiosity and interest people have for duck mussels. Observations from this tasting event supported the realization of the local ecological knowledge formation through sensory engagement.

Collaborative Experimentations and Knowledge Co-creation. Actors are working together towards creating knowledge about the duck mussel species through experimentation and trials because this is a project in which nobody knows everything. Actors are actively learning through testing, deploying, and experimenting with duck mussels. Fishermen have helped with initial experimentations as they already have the knowledge of the surroundings, and they have the equipment needed.

“I met him in the morning. He came with the mussels....we took my boat, and we drove out to the location where I had the anchoring and the buoys and attached the cages with lines to the anchoring grid that I had in place. So, I was basically the guy driving the mussels to the place where they were growing in the sea and bringing them back to the harbor.” – Fisherman A

“....it's this fish farmer that we have cooperated with, and then the fisherman that has mussel cages with their fish, fishing equipment, and nets. So, they have helped us with the transport and looking after it....they have been interested in it and they have helped us a lot....”- Fisheries Leader Advisor

Fisherman B mentioned that he is building his own cages for the mussels next summer as a trial-and-error experiment to create a greenhouse-like model.

“We have our own ideas, now I want to build a metal kind of a cage. That would be like a small-sized greenhouse with shelves and everything.”- Fisherman B

They have done lab tests to check for toxins in duck mussels, and now they plan on testing the nutrients of the mussels as a food source and reporting them, which highlights aspects of local knowledge formation.

“I have tested toxins and then the next step is to test for what kind of nutrients there are in the mussels and then to do some kind of reporting on this.....” – Project Manager

In this early stage, this knowledge is formed in collaboration between multiple community actors, such as members of the regional development organization, chefs, fishermen, researchers, and other community members involved. They are working with a community member to find solutions with current species to find solutions for the nutrient-polluted pond in Helsinki by building the knowledge.

“Collaboration with....so we had a meeting last week because he has been thinking about a pond near Helsinki. It's quite nutrified, and he wanted to have some new solutions for that. So now we are going to help him to get the right knowledge....” – Project Manager

As per the Fisheries Leader Advisor, they have already created a lot of knowledge, and they know a lot, but still, there are gaps in knowledge that need to be filled.

“So, we have learned a lot. We know something. We know how to get duck mussels edible and tasty....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Overall, these findings show that contributions of community actors in the early stage, with a combination of trial-based learning, experimentation, environmental observations, and sensory feedback, result in LEK formation, which lays the path for future community involvement and business model formation.

4.3 Motivations, Mechanisms, and Pathways for Community Engagement

The third aggregated dimension identified is Motivations, Mechanisms, and Pathways for Community Engagement in these regenerative practices. Community engagement mechanisms and drivers are not uniform in this ecosystem regenerative practice, but rather are driven by various motivations, values, opportunities, and economic aspects. The analysis shows community engagement and participation of key actors, as well as other local community members who support experimentation and other related activities in this early development stage.

Emotional, Cultural, and Environmental Drivers for Engagement. Communities are driven to engage in these ecosystem regenerative practices because of their deep emotional connections to the place, cultural pride, and environmental factors.

Love for the sea, surroundings, and place identity inspires communities to engage in these practices because they are afraid of something bad happening to their surroundings; therefore, this factor drives them to take action to protect nature.

“...what makes it actually unique, at least for us, who are born and raised here next to the sea, we appreciate the sea a lot. We know that the sea provides a lot....Here you always read some kind of catastrophe, so people are a little bit scared of what is happening with the ocean because their love for the ocean.... – Local Chef

“I think the interest and engagement in the surrounding environment is the driving factor so far that we can use. These mussels and floating gardens do something good for our own nearby water environment, and I think that’s the main factor and surely it will be the main factor for the coming years....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“And so, we are now very focused on keeping this harbor alive. And that’s why we also are perhaps more willing to do different things in new kinds of ways” – Fisherman B

Moreover, the local communities have concerns about marine ecosystems damage, and eutrophication in the Baltic Sea, which causes algae blooms. They are eager to get rid of algae blooms by taking nutrients out of the water. These regenerative practices will provide solutions for their concerns, driving them to engage in these practices.

“Why are the people interested in this? Because quite many have called me the last 10 years and asked, how they can get rid of all the algae that come in July at their summer cottage because it’s not that nice to go and swim....” – Project Manager

Curiosity, Novelty, and Excitement as a Local Product. The project manager mentioned that different motivations inspire community involvement depending on their interests. The Fisheries Leader Advisor mentioned that people are always interested in doing new things, therefore, this can be a driver for this type of new practice.

“Different people are keen on different things....they can be cleaning, biodiversity, aesthetic, or eating, so you can have different kinds of motivation and interests....” – Project Manager

“That’s interesting to see because people are actually interested in doing something like this....it’s new and people are interested. There are always people who look for new things and are interested in producing new things....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Fishermen are curious about new species that can survive in low-salinity Finnish waters. The chef is excited to experiment with new species, such as duck mussels. These factors drive them to get involved in this practice.

“I’ve been, of course, very curious about this. All kinds of possibilities of this duck mussels.... because the salinity is very low in this area....so I’ve always been curious about what kinds of species or plants that could work in our area....” – Fisherman B

“That’s why it’s really cool for me....But I’m really curious, and of course, I really like shellfish and seafood, and I do like to try a lot of food. And I’m really curious about techniques to do a lot of different things. So, I’m not afraid of using this new ingredient....” – Local Chef

Further, the chef mentioned the shift in Finnish food culture towards seafood, and he is optimistic about public acceptance of duck mussels when they get to know that this is a food that regenerates nature. The chef is really keen on using and promoting local ingredients.

“Like, for example, you can find blue mussels in stores now. But if you go back ten years in Finland, that was not common at all. So, I think now Finnish people, Finnish cuisine has been introduced to seafood. Everyone has tasted some kind of seafood....” – Local Chef

“I think in this matter I’m quite extreme. I really like this local thinking so I pushed it really far with local thinking....most population of Finland lives around the sea, so I think if we can get something that produces there and also is good for the ocean, I think that is more than enough to get the product to something that goes to the Finnish people’s, gastronomic hearts.” – Local Chef

Economic, Feasibility, and New Business Opportunity. Additionally, community members consider the economic factors and feasibility of engaging in these practices beyond emotional, cultural, and environmental reasons. Although this is not a driver at this point of early stage, it will have a big impact on broader community participation in the future.

Fishermen mentioned that they see mussel farming as easy and cost-efficient when compared to fishing, and the chef thinks the cooking process is not hard for mussels.

“Maybe a little bit or it is very much lower entry cost....of course, it needs to be properly managed, but it can be more cost-efficient for a smaller coastal fisherman to do something like this....” – Fisherman B

“....comparing the mussel cages to fish traps, it’s a very easy and simple setup....with the mussels....not a challenge, and also the cages with the

mussels, they're small, at least for the testing that we did, they could easily be moved by hand. You don't need any cranes or anything....” – Fisherman A

“With what I know now, I think it's a really easy product to cook. I think anyone who has cooked any seafood at home, any mussels, or any shellfish at home, they won't have a hard time at all to make this tasty....” – Local Chef

Fishermen are interested in the duck mussels as a new opportunity and expanding their product portfolio beyond fish, which adds more value to their existing business models with lower costs and profits.

“....my main interest is that if there is anything else that I can add to my product portfolio, other than fish, yeah, I'm very keen to follow how this unfolds....” – Fisherman A

“I think every fisherman, of course, is interested in how they can add some kind of value to their existing setup and if the entry cost is a little bit low and it's possible to make a profit....” – Fisherman B

Mainly, fishermen are interested in these practices if they generate extra income and profits with lower entry costs and minimal effort. Therefore, although they are positive about this practice, there is uncertainty around profitability and market readiness.

“...fishermen live on the water, from what the water gives, so if we find models that they could make some extra money on, yes, it will interest them, but we aren't there yet. That's the problem. We can't tell them that this is how you should do it, or at least try. We don't know enough....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“Hard to say if I'm going to start growing them in the future or not, because it would all depend on whether you can get some kind of profitability out of it. So, I think it's too early to tell at this stage. But I have a very positive attitude towards it....” - Fisherman A

Public Outreach, Awareness, Education, and Sensory Engagement Strategies. To create awareness and engage broader communities, they engaged in outreach strategies, visual communications, public events, media involvement, and educational activities. Community actors mentioned that since this is a new practice, they had to use smart ways to create public awareness. Also, they are working to take this message to the parents through their kids. The Executive Director of the regional development organization extensively discussed this strategy of taking the message to adults through kids.

“...we have to be a little bit smart to get our message forward....I usually have an aquarium with me with mussels, and then we also decided to try to have it in the afternoon, so every one of these 150 to 200 people is going to taste a mussel....” – Project Manager

“...we are working with a kindergarten right now, so maybe we can take the message through the children, to get parents to be interested. Because if the children want to do something, usually the parents want to support it....” – Project Manager

“I take adult mussels there because I want to show people what they look like, and I had this aquarium....Maybe six times now in different kinds of occasions, because.... here on the coast, there are not that many that know about duck mussels....” – Project Manager

“We cooked a little bit of the mussels and then we invited them to come and test it and write some stories, and both of them did, and quite big....local newspaper here....Finnish national TV news....” – Local Chef

Furthermore, there is a plan to build a demonstration site that is accessible for people to create awareness and educate the communities about these practices.

“Plan for a demonstration site that would be easy, accessible for people....A place that’s quite near Helsinki, so that people can go and watch how you can use floating islands and mussels to clean water.” – Project Manager

Overall, these motivations, mechanisms, and pathways illustrate how community engagement in regenerative ocean farming is encouraged by values, hands-on outreach, curiosity, and localness. Through the active contribution of community actors, these initiatives build a strong social foundation that can enable the creation of future regenerative business models.

4.4 Pathways for the Emergence of Regenerative Business Models

The fourth aggregated dimension explores how community actors imagine, experiment, and expect the potential commercialization of duck mussels. As of now, a formal business model does not exist since the case is in its early stages. However, the empirical data reveals the strategic imagination, market aspects, and cultural framing that lay the foundation for regenerative business model emergence through these regenerative ocean farming practices.

Gastronomic Framing and Cultural Narrative Building. Interviews placed duck mussels as a gastronomic novelty, framing restaurants as the main market. Duck mussels can be used in restaurants as a new, niche, exclusive, local, sustainable, and nutritious protein that brings cultural and environmental value.

“So, I think the market will be mostly restaurants....Restaurants that like to have something special on the menu and it's local, new, and exclusive....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“....I see more like restaurant products, and then the restaurant gets sustainable shellfish from Finland that are not imported....it's sustainable food. They have good lipids, proteins, and many minerals.” – Project Manager

“I think that it would probably depend on the price if they're super expensive, you can maybe find a niche at some restaurants....because it brings some value, with the environmental impacts. And it's like a new and fun thing to do....” – Fisherman A

Further, they explain the important role of chefs and restaurants in promoting and creating a demand for this new source of food. Restaurants can create cultural narratives and create a story behind the plate that's being served to the customers.

“....I think that restaurants by water....could be interesting because it's an image thing for them if they can grow, or at least it can be sourced from the neighbor or something....they create value. It's not only the mussel on the plate, but also all this history around it and background, and you can show people that it's interesting....Like you basically have a narrative to this....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“When you have these kinds of brave chefs and restaurants....I think that it has a lot to do with them. Also, how much are they willing to play with these mussels in the beginning....So it's very difficult for one fisherman who is trying to sell them. It has to come like a sort of demand from some kind of a buyer or something....” – Fisherman B

Additionally, the tasting event created curiosity and excitement among the guests, and a fisherman who participated in the event mentioned that it was very inspirational. The researcher attended this tasting event and observed the curiosity building among the guests, not only for the taste but also for the vision of having a new locally sourced product in the market.

“....I think the food was good enough to get excited. So, I think the reaction was that you can have some new product in the future, in a market that no one else tried, which is really cool.” - Local Chef

“....I think it was very inspirational. I liked it very much...” – Fisherman B

Framing duck mussels as a food source introduces them as a product as well as a way to build the early symbolic value needed for market legitimacy and creating a new culture.

Economic Viability and Requirements Needed for Commercialization. Interviewees described factors related to business viability, such as pricing, production scale, and market access, that play a crucial role in the emergence of future business models. Pricing was considered an important factor because if the prices are too high, it will be an issue introducing this to the consumer market. Therefore, it is important to check the price points as soon as the product is available.

“I think that the biggest thing after we have the product ready is to actually go and see how we can introduce it to the Finnish markets or even to export and check the price....my thinking is that if the mussels get some kind of price that's not like the lobster price. Everyone wanna use it and try it....” – Local Chef

“But if you wanna sell it on a large scale to the Finnish market, it should of course be relatively cheap when compared to other protein sources....” – Fisherman A

In addition, it was mentioned that there is a need for proper calculations to check the economic viability of duck mussel production because mussels do not weigh much, therefore, fisherman predicts that there should be a big volume to gain a profit. However, they cannot do any accurate calculations as of now because market demand and pricing are not known for the product.

“....they don't weigh that much either. Yeah, like 1 fish it can be 15 kilos, but I don't know a mussel, they weigh maybe 20 grams, 30 grams, or 50 grams. So, it's I think you would need a lot of them to create some value for the market....” – Fisherman A

“....perhaps very good to make some kind of calculations, but it's impossible to do at the moment because we don't know any pricing or demand and everything....So, it's very difficult for now to make such calculations” – Fisherman B

Fisherman A mentioned that long-term profitability is essential for the sustainability of duck mussels as a business, and proper production and sales models should be in place to get the

baby mussels and also to sell them after harvesting. He mentioned that it would be a curious, fun activity at the beginning, but this factor itself would not sustain this practice.

“I think in the beginning it’s fun for everyone to do a bit of testing and all that, but in the long term you need profitability, and you need to have somewhere to sell the mussels, and you need to get them at the right time and when they’re the right size....” – Fisherman A

Therefore, it can be seen that proper economic viability with accurate scaling and pricing data is important for the emergence of business models. Even though there are uncertainties, there are emerging entrepreneurial imaginations through job creation, new business opportunities, and multi-use models.

Entrepreneurial Imagination and Opportunity Recognition. According to the project manager, regenerative ocean farming can be a means of job creation around the world, resulting in a different type of business model emergence.

*“...if we have a crisis, and we need to create jobs....this could be for creating jobs. So then, this will be a very different approach to the business model....”
– Project Manager*

For Fisherman A, the most interesting factor would be the creation of new opportunities and adding value to their current business models, making it the driving factor to engage in this regenerative practice.

“For me, what I’d be interested in is mostly this new opportunity.... I think from the perspective of a fisherman, if we come to a point where duck mussels can be grown on a commercial scale, I think it would be very easy for a fisherman such as myself to....” – Fisherman A

There are possibilities for the emergence of different business models because, according to the project manager, it depends on the personal interests and motivations. Therefore, there can be business models related to food, biodiversity, ecosystem enhancement, re-circulation applications, and many more.

“....there are quite a lot of possibilities to develop different kinds of business models depending on what you are interested in. Are you interested in food? biodiversity? cleaning the water? And then you can also do re-circulation if you can't eat everything, maybe make a fertilizer or something that can develop the soil so you get better biodiversity there....we also can use it as food for animals....” – Project Manager

However, it is clear that regenerative business model application is still in the imagination phase and not yet executed because several barriers need to be crossed and navigated before the official commercialization happens, for example, figuring out the market size and profitability factors of the product.

“The biggest challenge with mussels is that I don’t know how many mussels you need to get for a good day’s work....If this is an industry that we want to grow and invest in, there needs to be profitability....so I’m not really sure, like where is the limit or where is the line where you can actually get like some kind of daily salary....” – Fisherman A

Members of Aktion Österbotten know how to make the people interested, but they are still figuring out the commercialization through local ecological knowledge formation activities. However, they remain optimistic about the future emergence of business models through these ecosystem regenerative practices.

“... We know enough to make people curious and make people try, but we don’t know enough how to get it on a commercial scale...but I think that in five years we will have some kind of production method so we could produce them on some scale....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

The researcher participated in the duck mussel business model workshop, where practical strategies for commercialization were discussed and explored. Although a set roadmap was not created, this workshop demonstrated the collaborative spirit and entrepreneurial curiosity that successfully matched commercial goals with ecological and cultural interests, reflecting the rising interest in regenerative business-oriented approaches.

Overall, empirical data reveal early pathways toward regenerative business models through these community-driven experiments, culinary framings, and economic reflections. Although there is no concrete business model yet, there are signs of future business models emerging through curiosity, cultural values, local identity, and care for nature. At this stage, regeneration is not only ecological but also creates an entrepreneurial spirit.

4.5 Barriers, Tensions, and Structural Limitations

The previous sections described four distinct aggregated dimensions derived through the Gioia method, however, one additional theme emerged repeatedly across the dataset, listing

the barriers, tensions, and structural limitations that impact every dimension of regenerative ocean farming (Figure 9).

Cultural and Social Barriers. There are persisting barriers to consumer acceptance due to cultural aspects such as the novelty of consuming mussels, and as Fisherman B mentioned, Finnish communities are quite conservative. Mussels are not a part of Finnish cuisine, it is new to the market, therefore demand for the product might be low, at least in the beginning, until consumer awareness is created.

“...we don't have this cultural norm of eating mussels here. So that's why it has probably never been eaten. It is an unknown item in that sense....of course, we are quite conservative in Finland with mussels and everything....” – Fisherman B

“It's not a part of our food culture in Finland. So, the question is, will normal people start to buy duck mussels.... I think it's quite a big threshold for normal households to buy mussels. At least we don't do it today....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

It is evident that deep-rooted cultural habits impact the initial demand and acceptance of a new product; therefore, to overcome this culinary novelty, strategies for awareness, narrative building, and visibility for the public must be implemented.

Regulatory and Legal Uncertainties. There are uncertainties about regularities around farming duck mussels due to the novelty of the product. According to fishermen, anyone can engage in this practice, however, there is a need to acquire a permit for the water. However, they predict that these processes will not be very complex.

“I don't necessarily think that you need to be registered as a commercial fisherman to grow mussels, but you would need to have the right to the water that you're using....” – Fisherman A

“For this, in my experience, you will need the permit for the water for the area where you put them, but since there is no feeding or anything like this, you shouldn't have to go through any difficult processes. It should be quite easy....” – Fisherman B

Due to the novelty of this product as a food, which has never been eaten before, this comes under the novel food category, therefore, this should go under certain legalities to be regulated as a food. There are many uncertainties and barriers around this process.

Authorities do not provide proper answers or methods for this process, and at the same time, it was predicted that it would be time-consuming and costly.

“How can we apply for duck mussels as a novel food? And I haven’t gotten the answers....I have already read all their links, but they don’t give straight answers....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“I mean, they don’t want to touch this subject unless they have to....I think the response is that you can do this if you want, and they have no reason to start investigating, unless something happens, I guess....” – Biologist Researcher

“I just think that it’s quite a big process, which will have quite a lot of costs. If I have understood it right, this novel food process is quite long and expensive...” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Uncertainties in Taste, Texture, and Product Handling. As mentioned before, since this is a new product as a food, there are significant uncertainties in cooking methods to obtain the right texture and flavor. As per the chef, more time is needed to experiment with recipes and handling techniques to create appealing and tasty dishes. A key challenge is that duck mussels absorb the taste of their local environment, resulting in varying flavors depending on water conditions. However, the chef sees this as a creative opportunity too, because controlling growth environments has the potential to customize flavor profiles based on culinary preferences.

“....but for the texture and stuff like that, I think I need a little bit more time, and I need the product to be stable to know exactly because you can play a lot around with it on how you treat them before you cook them....” – Local Chef

“I think the trick is finding the right place for them to grow to a nice size. But also, flavor-wise to have, maybe not too unique flavor, but approachable flavor....” – Local Chef

“....the new thing here is that with this mussel we can actually make them taste what we want, and that is really cool....” – Local Chef

Knowledge and Infrastructure Gaps. The main barrier to growing duck mussels is that there is no clear way to obtain the baby mussels, meaning there is a significant need for a hatchery to grow baby mussels to the right size before being distributed among the community members. This is the first step that needs to be solved to involve communities in this practice, and as discussed before, actors are trying different lab-based as well as natural methods to reproduce these mussels.

“The big thing is to get effective reproduction. That is the big thing....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

“So that's another reason to apply money for some hatchery for breeding of duck mussels....” – Biologist Researcher

“The main part in the project now, of course, would be to get the cycle started on how to get more of these mussels....” – Fisherman B

Also, at the duck mussel business model workshop, this issue of a lack of a clear hatchery process was repeatedly identified and discussed as a core barrier that needs to be overcome before scalable or inclusive engagement of the communities.

Further, there are no clear guidelines about the process of growing duck mussels, which is a major barrier to engaging communities in this practice. As explained clearly by Fisherman A, communities must be given clear guidance on where to get baby mussels, how to grow them, how to care for them, the infrastructure needed, how to harvest them, where to sell them if commercialized, and what kind of permits or permissions are needed. It is clear that many uncertainties need to be answered before engaging communities. However, these guidelines will be created in a few years as experimentation and the formation of LEK are done in the early-stage development of this initiative. According to the fisheries leader advisor, it will take a substantial time to create a proper handbook on how to grow these mussels because they are still experimenting and forming the knowledge.

“I think that first of all, there need to be some kind of proof of concept that need to be done so that any fisherman that is interested in adding some compliment to his fishery or interested in growing mussels have something to start from....what equipment do you need and how many mussels can you get and where do you buy them from and what kind of market channels can you distribute them to and in what conditions can they grow and what kind of permissions you need. I think that before any commercial fisherman could get into this, the concept needs to be in place.” – Fisherman A

“A handbook on how to grow mussels will take at least three years because we have to see how they grow....” – Fisheries Leader Advisor

Environmental and Technical Challenges. There are some unique environmental and climate challenges for regenerative ocean farming in Finland due to the low salinity of the Finnish Sea and the severe winter conditions. As discussed before, community actors recognized these low salinity conditions and are adopting their methods for these surroundings and doing experiments to create knowledge around this.

“....comparing Finland to other countries, I think we have some challenges here that you wouldn't face in other areas and oceans, like we have brackish water. So that means that we have actually quite a few species that thrive in our waters....But I think with the duck mussels, they seem to be okay with the water, even though they are from freshwater....But then, of course, we also have ice conditions in the winter....This is maybe more like a technical question, but the anchoring in the way it was done with the mussels....you would probably need to have a different kind of anchoring....” – Fisherman A

During the discussion with the executive director, it was highlighted that there are no proper methods to check and validate the results of the water-cleaning processes of mussels in natural habitats. This gap in practical measurements was seen as a main barrier because it is essential to obtain reliable and visible data to create confidence and trust within communities to make them engage in this practice.

Overall, the structural, cultural, environmental, and regulatory barriers depict the early-stage nature of the regenerative ocean farming in Finland. These challenges can be understood as frictions that shape the localized, grounded, and adaptive evolution of ecosystem regenerative practices. As ongoing experimentation continues to create deeper local ecological knowledge, many of these barriers, tensions, and limitations can be navigated, revealing the path for more inclusive, scalable, and long-term ecosystem regenerative practices and business models.

5 Discussion

This chapter discusses the key interpretive and novel insights derived from the four aggregated dimensions described in the findings chapter. Moving beyond explaining the aggregated dimensions, this chapter connects these insights with the theoretical background outlined in Chapter 2, focusing on how communities contribute to the early-stage development of ecosystem regenerative practices.

Figure 11. Key Interpretations Discussed in this Chapter (Author Generated)

This section is structured around five key interpretations that cut across the aggregated dimensions, offering a deeper understanding of the dynamics observed in the case. This section lays the foundation for the empirical model that answers the research question, which will be introduced in the next chapter. The visual guide for the interpretive synthesis of this chapter is provided in Figure 11.

5.1 Community Actor Roles in Early-Stage Ecosystem Regenerative Practices

The researcher identified different community roles that contribute to ecosystem regenerative practices. These roles were derived through the synthesis of the literature on community involvement in nature regeneration (See Table 4). These roles include: knowledge holders, such as local and Indigenous communities (González-Torres et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2023; Montenegro et al., 2024; Sinclair et al., 2024), initiators who set the vision and implement initial actions (Sides, 2023; Sinclair et al., 2024), collaboration and co-management where communities get together and manage together (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Lähde et al., 2024; Montenegro et al., 2024), hands-on contributors who participate in active regenerative practices (Clarke et al., 2021; Koko et al., 2024; Palmer et al., 2022), monitors and stewards who track the impact with long-term responsibility (Haq et al., 2023; Impedovo et al., 2024; Woelfle-Erskine, 2018), and public advocates who contribute in raising awareness and policy changes (Impedovo et al., 2024; Lähde et al., 2024).

However, these roles can be identified in various stages of regenerative practices from the initiation to the more mature practices, and all are not always visible in the very early stages, when the initiative is still envisioned, experimented with, and knowledge is being formed.

In this study, regenerative practice is in its early development stage. Therefore, in this context, not all roles identified in the literature synthesis were observable. However, the findings revealed the prominent presence of the “*Initiator*” role, which the researcher conceptualized as a community actor role during the literature synthesis. While the exact term Initiator was not explicitly used in the reviewed literature, the concept emerged throughout, capturing the type of community actors who initiate these practices, which was then strongly supported by the empirical findings.

Initiator can be defined as individuals or an organization that takes the first strategic steps in launching these ecosystem regenerative practices. This role extends beyond facilitating participation or implementing technical work. Initiators create and are responsible for establishing the foundational structure, designing the vision and goals, securing funding and resources, and actively collaborating with external community members to involve them in the initiative. In simple words, initiators are the foundational pillars who transform a regenerative idea into an actionable reality. In this study, the initiators were the three key

individuals from Aktion Österbotten: the Executive Director, the Fisheries Leader Advisor, and the Project Manager.

The findings reveal how initiators think long-term, to find solutions to ecological degradation by engaging in novel activities. Their vision is to produce food in a regenerative way so that it also cleans the water, regenerating the ocean. Initiators are visionaries and system designers whose tasks go beyond simple operational work, where they move the regenerative vision and logic forward even if there is no formal roadmap to follow, which is clear in this case study.

Further, it was evident that initiators collaborate to bring together external community actors into the process. In the case study, a local chef, fishermen, and a biologist researcher were included in the initial phases for knowledge, experimentation, and engagement activities. These actors do not fall under the initiator role but rather can be described as “*Early-stage Collaborators*.” As the literature explains, collaborators are community actors acting together with external stakeholders by co-designing, co-implementing, and co-managing regenerative practices for successful results (eg, Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Lähde et al., 2024; Montenegro et al., 2024). However, the local chef, fishermen, and biologist researcher do not perform all the functions mentioned in the literature. Therefore, their role can be named as early-stage collaborators, meaning community actors who contribute to early-stage regeneration initiatives by participating in localized experiments, knowledge formation, and engagement activities enabled by initiators.

The findings reveal that early-stage collaborators bring support, enthusiasm, place-based knowledge, and credibility to the initiative implemented by the initiators. Therefore, their role is not passive but rather enabled by the strategic foundation laid by the initiators.

Other community actor roles the researcher identified in the literature synthesis, such as knowledge holders, monitors, stewards, and policy reformers, were not yet fully present due to the early-stage phase of this case. Ecosystem regenerative practice is still in its preliminary phase in Ostrobothnia, and these community actor roles are just beginning to develop. With time more clearer roles may emerge within this case.

Although both the initiator and collaborator roles were present in the reviewed literature, they were not explicitly named in these terms. Therefore, these terms were synthesized by the researcher during the literature review (See section 2.4). In the literature, collaborator

roles were discussed in more stable or mature regenerative practices; thus, this study refined this concept to capture the unique early-stage dynamics of the role by naming it as “early-stage collaborators.”

In conclusion, the initiator was identified as a foundational community actor role in early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices. Along with them, early-stage collaborators also play an important supporting role. Identifying these different key community roles is important to understand that regenerative initiatives are not spontaneous or widely community-driven from the beginning, but rather carefully initiated and structured through the strategic community contributions of a few actors.

5.2 Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge (Strategic-LEK) Formation

The formation of LEK was strongly observed in this case study. In the initiation itself, community actors recognized the need to build ecological knowledge from the ground up because of the novelty of using duck mussels, a freshwater species, to regenerate the ocean while producing food. Findings demonstrate that the knowledge was not inherently present from lived experiences and livelihoods as described in the literature (Charnley et al., 2007, Davis and Wagner, 2003). Thus, initiators began to create strategic and project-driven LEK with the support of early-stage collaborators, which literature reflects as LEK formation through collaborations between different stakeholders (Albareda and Branzei, 2024; Emard et al., 2024; Ruddle and Davis, 2011).

LEK was not gradually accumulated but rather formed in a more rapid, targeted phase to achieve specific goals. While the literature notes that LEK can be adaptive (Joa et al., 2018; Leithäuser and Holzhaacker, 2020), the empirical findings demonstrate a proactive and more organized approach to LEK creation as a result of the regenerative initiative. They performed various structured experiments, collaborative learning, and iterative engagement activities to build the knowledge needed. This aligns with the understanding that LEK is formed through observations, experiences, and trial and error (Charnley et al., 2007; Hilary and Martin, 1999). However, the difference in the case study is that this knowledge is being generated purposefully to achieve ecological and economic goals through experimentation, observations, and trial-and-error. Therefore, this can be named as “*Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge (Strategic-LEK)*” formation.

Findings suggest that new community roles are being formed as a result of the LEK formation, which goes beyond the community actor role of knowledge holder that was identified through the literature synthesis (González-Torres et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2023; Montenegro et al., 2024; Sinclair et al., 2024). The case study reveals active community roles that enable, co-create, and innovate the knowledge for the strategic formation of LEK.

In the regenerative ocean farming initiative, community actors such as the members of Aktion Österbotten, fishermen, chefs, and researchers actively engaged in creating new knowledge, using their existing place-based knowledge and engaging in observation, experimentation, and sensory engagement. These roles indicate that LEK was not passively inherited in this case but co-created, purposefully combining scientific and hands-on local experimentation with forward-looking processes, which illustrates the early-stage development of this ecosystem regenerative practice.

Moreover, in this case, knowledge was not only about scientific discovery, but it was a mix of a deep local, cultural, sensory, culinary, and scientific process (Emard et al., 2024; Joa et al., 2018; Ruddle and Davis, 2011; Toner et al., 2023). For example, the tasting event held at the local restaurant allowed ecological understanding to be translated into gastronomic insights. These events supported building knowledge around the cooking techniques, texture, and flavor of duck mussels as a food source. In addition, these experiences generated interest and grounded ecological learning through emotional and cultural engagement.

The empirical findings suggest that, in this case, LEK is not merely a byproduct of long-term interactions with nature but rather a strategically initiated process to achieve the goal of establishing and legitimizing the regenerative practice and future business approaches. Rather than adapting existing practices, community actors co-create new knowledge, aligning with the place-based and adaptive nature of LEK (Karnad, 2022, Aswani et al., 2020, Joa et al., 2018, Emard et al., 2024). Building strategic LEK is essential in this case to engage broader communities in the future, and this lays the foundation for future business models. This enables product feasibility, cultural acceptability, market appeal, and place-based legitimacy.

In this case, strategic-LEK emerged as the invisible infrastructure of early-stage regenerative practices, which was a co-produced, experimented, and deeply contextual knowledge that

enables the future emergence of regenerative entrepreneurship and business models (Rahman et al., 2024).

In conclusion, it can be suggested that community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices by strategically creating new LEK through experimentation, observation, collaboration, and cultural engagement. LEK is not inherently present but rather strategically formed, which can be named Strategic-LEK, where community actors are not just passive knowledge holders but active designers of these knowledge systems, contributing to wider community engagement in regenerative practices as well as the future emergence of regenerative business models.

5.3 Motivational Drivers in Early-Stage Community Engagement

The literature reviewed highlighted that communities play an important role in nature regeneration because their active contributions are essential for effective, long-term, and fair outcomes in various fields (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Koko et al., 2024; Maniraho et al., 2023; Palmer et al., 2022; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021). Literature mentions different ways communities contribute to these practices through knowledge, ownership, long-term commitment, capacity building, economic incentives, and engaging in collaborative efforts. However, the findings from the case study reveal a different picture, where community engagement is focused and limited. This reflects the early-stage nature of the initiative, where engagement is strategically cultivated rather than spontaneously spread.

Engagement at this stage is primarily handled by initiators and a few early-stage collaborators, by engaging in experiments, trials, and laying the foundation for broader public involvement. The findings reflect that initiators are focusing on building credibility, clarifying the vision and goals, and building LEK before involving communities at a large scale. Their contributions in this early stage indicate a strategic and deliberate approach for building the conditions needed before broader inclusion.

The main motivational driver that pushed initiators to engage in this regenerative practice was the *foundational vision* of “producing food in a way that cleans the water.” This primary vision was the initial motivator for initiators, which was then combined with the immediate driver of needing to *collaboratively build LEK*, which drove the engagement of early-stage

collaborators. While the literature reviewed highlights the importance of community involvement and LEK in regeneration from a broader perspective such as economic incentives, as a solution for the existing environmental crisis, and pre-existing social strategies for environmental stewardship (See Table 3), the findings suggest a different perspective that is driven by the exciting “why” (the regenerative vision), and the curious “how” (the need for building LEK) as the foundational, shared driver for initial participation. Therefore, it can be suggested that a compelling vision, when clearly communicated, can drive the interest of community engagement, which draws curious community actors, problem-solvers, nature-lovers, and explorers interested in trying new things. The literature focuses on more mature practices, whereas this case study emphasizes the unique characteristics of an early-stage ecosystem regenerative practice driven by initial vision exploration and engagement.

Another significant motivational driver expressed in the findings was the role of *novelty*, which lays the foundation *for pioneering and being an ambassador*, which emerges in this early stage. The opportunity to be involved in something new and untested drew the interest of the local chef and fishermen B. Although not explicitly described in the reviewed literature for this study, the empirical findings show the inherent human nature for exploration, innovation, and being part of something groundbreaking as a powerful motivational driver for community engagement. As mentioned by the local chef, he considers himself an ambassador at this stage, and Fisherman B expressed that being a pioneer at this stage excites him. This special effect of being a starter attracts individuals who are comfortable with trying new things, dealing with uncertainty, and are motivated by the challenge of creating something new. This aspect can be seen in the very early stages before broader community engagement, where the motivational drivers might change by social norms, economic incentives, or other drivers as the engagement grows, as mentioned in the literature (See Table 3).

As highlighted in the literature, economic incentives play a role in attracting communities to engage in regenerative practices (eg, Koko et al., 2024; Pourzakarya and Bahramjerdi, 2021; Qu et al., 2017; Whyte et al., 2024). This was especially seen in communities whose livelihoods are connected to nature (eg, Ahmed et al., 2022; Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2023). Although the early-stage contribution of community actors does not depend on economic incentives, it can be understood from the findings that tangible benefits such as

economic feasibility, extra income, and profitability will play an important role in broader community engagement in the long term. For example, fishermen consider the lower entry costs and the potential to diversify their product portfolio as motivators for long-term engagement. However, they acknowledge that uncertainty around profitability is a critical condition that might decide their longer-term participation beyond experimentation activities. The mentality of wait-and-see was evidently seen with the fishermen, as it was important for them to understand economic aspects. Despite this, they were very interested in supporting and engaging in this early development stage with the initiators.

Furthermore, place-based ownership identity enforces this belongingness and responsibility of protecting nature (González-Torres et al., 2024). Empirical findings suggest that this sense of ownership is enhanced by *emotional and cultural attachments* such as love for the sea, desire to keep the harbor alive, and concerns about algae blooms. This shows that motivation for participation is also driven by the love for their surrounding nature (Albareda and Branzei, 2024; González-Torres et al., 2024; Sinclair et al., 2024).

Another prominent and novel insight that was not found in the analyzed literature was *gastronomy* as a motivational driver to engage communities. For example, the local chef was interested in experimenting with a new local ingredient to contribute to integrating a locally sourced novel sustainable food source. Collaboration with the chef and hosting tasting events cultivated excitement among the invited guests. The culinary aspect offered tangibility by connecting ecology with gastronomy, culture, identity, and creativity, which will be further discussed in the next section.

In conclusion, the empirical findings highlight underexplored motivational drivers in early-stage community engagement, whereas the literature focuses on broader participation in more mature practices. This study revealed motivational drivers such as vision, curiosity, novelty, local pride, and pioneering, as well as the role of gastronomy, which lays the foundation for broader community engagement and the emergence of regenerative business models in the future.

5.4 Gastronomy as Legitimation in Regenerative Engagement

The literature reviewed does not explicitly mention gastronomy as a part of regenerative practices. However, the findings of this study highlight a novel empirical contribution where gastronomy serves as a tangible and cultural foundation between ecosystem regeneration and community engagement. In this case, the product development was done through gastronomy, where the engagement of the chef enabled the development of duck mussels as a new dish. This experimentation by chefs created new tastings through sensory experience, narrative construction, and cultural influence. Gastronomy goes beyond simply being a motivator by supporting the familiarization of the unfamiliar to the community.

Findings demonstrate that mussels are culturally not known in the Finnish culinary culture, therefore, tasting events hosted supported introducing duck mussels through taste and sensory experience. The local chef experimented with the duck mussels as well as planned for further testing to create delicious dishes supporting culinary legitimacy. As of this stage, duck mussels cannot be commercialized; therefore, tasting events offered direct exposure to the product. The literature explains the role of collaborations with community actors for ecosystem regeneration practices (eg, Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Lähde et al., 2024; Montenegro et al., 2024), and in this case, chefs function as cultural translators by transforming this novel species into an exploratory dish for the public. In addition, these culinary experimentations are a method of LEK formation.

The findings suggest that gastronomic storytelling that aligns with local identity and environmental values supports building trust in this regenerative practice. The local chef framed duck mussels as a local innovation that is a locally sourced, healthy, and sustainable protein. The literature review explains that the emotional and cultural connection to a place could be a driver for engagement (Albareda and Branzei, 2024; Sinclair et al., 2024; González-Torres et al., 2024). Therefore, it can be suggested that in this case, gastronomy acts as an emotional and cultural factor allowing the engagement of community members in this novel practice.

There is a narrative built behind this ocean regenerative practice, which is connected by the culinary discourse of the duck mussel. This emphasizes that regenerative ocean farming is not only about regenerating the ocean but also a form of obtaining an exclusive, local, sustainable, and healthy protein. Findings reveal terms such as “a special on the menu,” “new

and exclusive,” and “a product with a story,” which support this culinary discourse around duck mussels. Therefore, this case paints the contribution to regenerative practices as a broader story going beyond environmental regeneration by highlighting local innovation and cultural pride.

Although there are no commercial activities yet, the gastronomic success of duck mussels plays a huge role in ecological, cultural, and market legitimacy. As mentioned before, this is not a known food in Finland; therefore, tasting events increase community awareness and create a demand. The literature explains value-added products as a type of business models that emerge through regenerative practices (eg, Ahmed et al., 2022; Koko et al., 2024). Similarly, in this case, gastronomy acts as a form of pre-market validation, showing how a regenerative business could be when this is commercialized.

In conclusion, the findings reveal that community actors, especially in this case, chefs, contribute to early-stage regenerative practices by embedding novelties in cultural context and transforming them into tangible, trusted, and sensory experiences. This lays the foundation for the emergence of regenerative business models centred on local sourcing, sustainability, and value-added product innovation.

5.5 Laying the Groundwork for Regenerative Business Models

It is evident that a formal regenerative business model for duck mussels is not yet in operation, however, the findings reveal the presence of an early-stage business logic mindset and imaginaries that lay the foundation for future regenerative business model emergence. Findings show that the end goal of this initiative is to establish a regenerative business model in the future that includes ecological, social, and economic benefits. The literature reviewed showcases business in regeneration from two angles, one where regenerative business approaches emerge through nature regeneration practices, although not illustrated explicitly (eg, Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Kapletia et al., 2023; Haq et al., 2023; Qu et al., 2017; Whyte et al., 2024; Zytkoskee et al., 2024) and the other where the transformation of regenerative business models in an organizational level (Das and Bocken, 2024; Hahn and Tampe, 2021; Konietzko et al., 2023; Muñoz and Branzei, 2021). However, this case study, which is still in its early development phase, illustrates the pathway to how a community-driven regenerative practice can lay the foundation for future business approaches.

Although there is no formal business model yet in this case, there is an alignment with the core principles and characteristics of regenerative business models as described in the literature review. Literature highlights that regenerative business models co-evolve and co-create with nature, understanding that it is one system and cannot operate in isolation, and is embedded in a SES (Hahn and Tampe, 2021; Konietzko et al., 2023). Community actors in this case understand that humans are interdependent on natural systems, which was one of the major reasons behind the initiation of this project. Further, initiators involved various community actors for early-stage development activities, aligning with the multistakeholder value creation characteristic described in the literature by creating and delivering value at multiple stakeholder levels through collaborations (Das and Bocken, 2024; Konietzko et al., 2023). In addition, the literature review emphasizes that regenerative business focuses on addressing place-based needs by focusing on unique ecological and social requirements of the local environment (Slawinski et al., 2019). This aligns with the vision and goal of the initiators because they designed a system suitable for Finland and to address the place-specific issues. The literature also discusses how some regenerative practices resulted in regenerative farming and aquaculture, value-added processing and product development, job creation, ecotourism, and nature-based enterprises (Ahmed et al., 2022; Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Haq et al., 2023; Kapletia et al., 2023; Lähde et al., 2024; Montenegro et al., 2024; Qu et al., 2017; Sinclair et al., 2024; Whyte et al., 2024; Zytoskee et al., 2024). Aligning with this, the findings reveal early imaginations of duck mussels as a regenerative business model, mainly as a gastronomic novelty, as well as potential livelihood diversification and extra income generation of fishermen, and even job creation around the world.

The findings reveal that the initial stages of regenerative ocean farming lay the foundation for entrepreneurial spirit, where community actors largely engage in experimentation and LEK creation. These practices, like hands-on experimentations and observations, cultivate the conditions needed for future locally adapted regenerative business models. For example, experimenting with species that can thrive in low-salinity water conditions in Finland. This shows the learning, innovation, and problem-solving characteristics of the initiation phase, which then contributes entrepreneurial mindset for the future creation of regenerative business models within the community.

As described in the above section, the role of chefs and restaurants plays a huge role in this initiative, especially in securing market legitimacy. The findings suggest a novel pathway of

introducing regenerative products through culinary narratives created around the novel product. It is evident that in this case, duck mussels are framed as a local, sustainable, exclusive, healthy, and unique gastronomic experience to create the path of restaurant-based business models and entrepreneurship in the future.

It can be suggested that regenerative business models in the community context initiate from a foundation of cultural values and commitment to nature regeneration, which is driven by LEK formation. In Finland, the initiative was started with a vision to produce food while cleaning the water, which led to hands-on trial activities and collaborative engagement for LEK formation. As discussed before, this was primarily driven by community motivations and connections to nature before any business or economic incentives become a driver.

In conclusion, it can be suggested that community actors do not merely wait for formal business systems to emerge but rather actively work to create them. They lay the social-ecological and market foundation through hands-on experimentation, cultural framing, and ecological adaptation, which lays the foundation for regenerative business model emergence. Contributions of community actors in this early-stage support shaping, directing, and legitimizing regenerative business approaches.

6 Conclusion

This study aims to explore and understand how community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and how these contributions lay the foundation for future regenerative business model emergence, answering the research question:

“How do community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices, and how do their contributions lay the foundations for the emergence of regenerative business models?”

In an era of accelerating environmental crisis, understanding how ecosystem regenerative approaches emerge in local communities is significantly important. This thesis focused on a new approach to nature regeneration, in which the community in Ostrobothnia, Finland, contributes to regenerative ocean farming by participating in strategic initiation, knowledge formation, experimentation, and engagement activities during the early stages of development of this practice.

This study addresses a clear knowledge gap in existing literature. Although there is an increasing focus on regeneration literature, it often focuses on community involvement and business approaches as two separate domains, rather than examining the role of communities in laying the foundation for both regenerative practices and regenerative business model emergence. Therefore, this study bridges this gap by analyzing community actor contributions to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and exploring how these contribute to the emergence of regenerative business model approaches.

This chapter aims to answer the research question of the study directly and concisely using the empirical model developed. Followed by the theoretical contributions, practical implications, limitations, and recommendations for future research.

6.1 Answering the Research Question of the Study

This study demonstrates that community actors contribute significantly to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices through strategic initiation and experimental collaboration driven by motivational, cultural, and visionary aspects. As the key contribution of this thesis,

an empirical model was developed to explain how these contributions develop and how they collectively lay the foundation for future regenerative outcomes (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Empirical Model Developed to Answer the Research Question of the Study (Author Generated)

This model answers the research question of this study. It first illustrates how community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices, and then shows how those contributions enable and prepare conditions for the co-emergence of regenerative business pathways and ecosystem renewal. The model is structured in an interconnected, layered, process-driven manner.

The initiative begins with the Initiators, who are motivated by a regenerative vision grounded in regenerative imagination. They establish the strategic vision and foundation needed for this regenerative practice to begin. Then they collaborate with Early-Stage Collaborators, who were motivated by factors such as novelty, curiosity, love for nature, and pioneering interest.

Together, these actors engaged in the co-creation of Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge (Strategic-LEK). This knowledge is not inherent or formed through lived experiences, but rather, purposefully and dynamically formed rapidly through local experimentation, gastronomy, hands-on trials, observations, and sensory experiences. This lays a culturally and socially embedded foundation.

This foundation enables Cultural and Market Anchoring for this novel product by using knowledge to familiarize the unfamiliar. Gastronomy plays a key role in this stage by developing novel locally sourced food, validating taste, and storytelling to create awareness and an emotional connection to the regenerative practice. This anchoring is important to build public awareness and trust, which lays the foundation for broader community engagement.

Finally, these community actor contributions prepare the Conditions for the Co-Emergence of Regenerative Outcomes. There are two interconnected outcomes: ecosystem regeneration and the emergence of entrepreneurial pathways for regenerative business. These outcomes are interconnected because one cannot exist without the other, and are the results of the same community-driven practices. These outcomes are deeply place-based, rooted in local knowledge, values, culture, and identity.

Overall, this empirical model demonstrates that community actors are not just participants in ecosystem regenerative practices. They initiate, shape, and legitimise these practices, emphasizing the important role played by community actors. Their contributions create social-ecological, cultural, and entrepreneurial foundations for regenerative outcomes such

as ecosystem regeneration and business innovation. In this sense, ecosystem regeneration is enabled by the visionary work of communities acting with place-based imaginations.

In conclusion, this empirical model answers the research question by clearly showing how community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices through vision, collaboration, knowledge formation, and how these contributions prepare the conditions for the emergence of regenerative business models rooted in local culture, knowledge, and environmental care.

6.2 Theoretical Contributions

This thesis makes five main theoretical contributions to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and regenerative business model formation. First, it defines the role of the “Initiator,” which is a foundational community actor role in the early stages of regenerative practices. Although the literature reviewed does not explicitly define these roles, the synthesis of the literature identified the role of the initiator, which was further elaborated with concrete empirical evidence. This study defines the initiator as an individual who takes the first steps to strategically establish the foundational structure, design the vision, secure resources, and actively collaborate with external stakeholders, providing the lens to understand the initiation and leadership required to recognize community-led ecosystem regenerative practices. Further, the role of collaborators identified through the literature synthesis was refined to introduce the term “Early-Stage Collaborators” to define the role relevant to the early-stage phase. These individuals contribute with limited capacity, mainly by supporting experimentation, LEK formation, and engagement activities that are enabled by the initiators.

Second, this study advances the understanding of Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) by introducing the concept of “Strategic-LEK” that is not merely inherited or passively accumulated through long-term lived experiences or livelihood, but rather actively formed through experimentation, collaboration, and sensory engagement. Strategic-LEK is formed from the ground up by diverse community actors involved in the early stages of this novel regenerative practice.

Third, this study identified novel motivational drivers that are specific to the early stages of community engagement in ecosystem regeneration, which include regenerative vision, curiosity, novelty, desire to pioneer and be an ambassador in something new, and the role of gastronomy. These roles go beyond economic incentives and responses to ecological crises as identified in the literature because the literature reviewed often focused on more mature practices. In this case, gastronomy was identified as a powerful tool for legitimizing novel regenerative practices as a mechanism of familiarizing the unfamiliar through sensory experiences for novel products like duck mussels.

Fourth, the findings highlight how these community-driven contributions serve as preconditions for regenerative business model emergence, rather than simply modifying established businesses and value chains. This bridges the gap where literature often treats community engagement and regenerative business models as two separate domains, by providing insights into how community actor contribution in the early phase of regeneration establishes the path and conditions for future regenerative business model emergence.

Finally, although this study does not claim Biocentric Work by Albareda and Branzei (2024) is currently present in the empirical case, it contributes to this emerging framework by describing the strategic pre-conditions including community groundwork, LEK formation, early engagement mechanisms, and processes that may serve as the foundation for future biocentric work to emerge. First, it connects the cycle of material abduction to the Strategic-LEK formation, as community actors iteratively observe biophysical anomalies and engage in experimental, place-based learning processes. Second, the findings align with the cycle of relational intercession, where, in this case, initiators and early-stage collaborators strategically cooperated to initiate the regenerative practice and build LEK. Together, these contributions advance the theoretical understanding of how early-stage community contributions, through strategic-LEK formation and cooperative engagement, lay the foundation for ecosystem regenerative practices aligned with Biocentric Work.

6.3 Practical Implications

This study offers several practical implications for individuals involved in initiating, designing, supporting, and participating in early-stage regenerative practices. First, the findings highlight the important role of community-driven vision as the foundation for

ecosystem regenerative practices. Practitioners and policymakers should understand the important role played by initiators in laying the foundation, building the structure, engaging external stakeholders, and establishing a shared vision before formal business approaches begin. Thus, it is crucial to recognize and support these roles through funding, facilitation, and long-term trust to strengthen these regenerative efforts.

A new implication identified was the role of gastronomy as a legitimizing and engagement tool. Sensory engagement and storytelling are important in early-stage regeneration in order to familiarise the public with unfamiliar products and create awareness. Therefore, approaches related to chefs, restaurants, public events, and culinary experiences should be given importance as a part of the regenerative strategy, especially when it involves novel food-based practices.

This study underpins the importance of supporting the invisible and emergent work that is done before formal structures or certifications exist, which results in more locally rooted, culturally aligned, and ecologically regenerative business models. Further, the early-stage collaborators identified in this study are not simply side players but rather key partners engaging in activities to make this vision a reality.

Finally, this thesis brings value to the initiators of this regenerative journey in Ostrobothnia. Their courage and interest to begin without a clear roadmap, engage external stakeholders, and envision a future where nature regeneration, business, and entrepreneurship are interconnected showcase their innovation and care for nature, which should be recognized and supported. Initiators and early-stage collaborators go beyond simply being participants; they co-create knowledge and engage in experimentation, working towards a shared vision with a deep commitment to place, people, and the planet. This research captures only a small part of their ongoing work and encourages future practitioners, institutions, and funders to recognize and support such initiatives as the basic building blocks of ecosystem regeneration.

6.4 Methodological Reflections and Limitations

This study offers important insights into community contributions to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices, however, there are several limitations to the study. This research is

based on a single qualitative case study in Ostrobothnia, Finland, which might limit the generalizability of the findings. This case was purposefully selected because of its exploration and novelty characteristics; therefore, the findings are based on the formative phase rather than mature or long-term phases. Therefore, these findings do not describe conclusions on regenerative business models or ecological impacts. As stated by Creswell (2013), the goal of qualitative studies is not generalization but to develop an in-depth understanding of a specific context.

The sample consisted of key initiators and early-stage collaborators, which was small and specific for the context but rich in depth as described in Section 3.5. This has the potential to limit the full representation of broader community perspectives, of those less involved or not yet involved at this stage. Further, the interpretive nature of qualitative studies and the researcher's active role may introduce subjectivity (Creswell and Poth, 2018). However, as described in Chapter 3, subjectivity was addressed through different methods to enhance the trustworthiness of the study.

6.5 Directions for Future Research

This study contributes to understanding how community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and how their contributions support the emergence of future regenerative business models. However, further research is needed to explore how these processes evolve with time, thus, longitudinal studies could explore similar initiatives in their mature phases with established practices, business models, and ecological outcomes that have gone beyond initiation phases with the support of community actor contributions. This could further deepen the knowledge of community actor roles identified in this study, as well as explore other roles that emerge over time.

In addition, comparative studies across different ecosystems or countries could provide transferability of these findings and identify similarities and differences between cases. Another noteworthy exploration would be further investigation of Strategic-LEK and the role of gastronomy as a cultural and market legitimization tool.

Finally, there is the possibility of exploring how discursive and storytelling practices influence broader community engagement in regenerative practices, which could help bridge the gap between Biocentric Work and the strategic pre-work that was identified in this thesis.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. SLR Process

Appendix 2. Number of Articles by Journals and Publication Forum Rating (JUFO)

Appendix 3. Number of Articles by the Year of Publication

Appendix 4. Theories and Concepts Identified in the Initial Set of Literature

Theory	Count
Social-Ecological Systems (SES)	3
Theory of Change (ToC)	2
Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK)	2
Nature Based Solutions	2
Global Production Network (GPN) Theory	1
Community Resilience	1
Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA)	1
Land-Sea Interactions (LSI)	1
Social Capital Theory	1
Ecological Psychology Theory	1
Biocentric Work	1
Post-Normal Science (PNS) Theory	1
Intersectionality Theory	1
Diffusion of Innovations Theory	1
Epistemic Justice Theory	1
Schwartz's Human Values Theory	1
Cultural Ecosystem Services (CES)	1
Forest Landscape Restoration (FLR) Theory	1
Social Innovation	1
Regenerative Development	1
Transformative Learning Theory	1
Multispecies Commons	1
Social Justice Theory	1
Social Learning Theory	1
Deliberative Democracy Theory	1
Middle-Range Theory	1

Appendix 5. Ecosystem Distribution in the Initial Set of Literature

Appendix 6. Work Done in the Initial Literature Review using Biocentric Work

Biocentric Work Elements	Description
Biomanipulation	<p>Communities involved in restoring the marine ecosystems. <i>"Local farmers in the Cox's Bazar coastal area including the Bakkhali river estuary, Inani, and St. Martin's Island, have recently been carrying out seaweed cultivation....To date, around 200–300 farmers along Cox's Bazar coast are engaged in seaweed farming...."</i> (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024) <i>"Farmers are currently practicing long-line and horizontal net methods for the seaweed farming in the southeast coastal region."</i> (Ahmed et al., 2022)</p> <p>Communities involved restoring Terrestrial ecosystems. <i>"From seed collection to direct seeding and monitoring, community groups were influential in enabling restoration practices in the Chapada dos Veadeiros region.....Mechanical soil preparation for direct seeding"</i> (Montenegro et al., 2024) <i>"People planted more trees, more species of trees, and more native trees in communal reserve...Residents planted and maintained trees through mingas (communal work parties), initially weekly and then 3–6 times a year for maintenance."</i> (Wilson and Coomes, 2019)</p> <p>Communities involved in restoring terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems. <i>"In the project, landscape management has included extensive restoration aimed to reduce erosion, increase grazing vegetation-cover, and reduce river silt loads."</i> (Qiu et al., 2022) <i>"The practice of ecological restoration...These interventions include activities ranging from plant propagation to river rerouting, and are done with the intention of bringing about desirable futures in response to ecosystem degradation."</i> (Sides, 2023)</p>
Biofacilitation	<p>Facilitation in Marine Ecosystems <i>"Scenario 1 integrates marine debris management with local cultural education, offering workshops and training sessions that teach practical debris collection skills...."</i> (Koko et al., 2024) <i>"Farmers can take the training on seaweed farming from the local fisheries extension office and can achieve self-sufficiency by cultivating seaweed in the nearby intertidal areas."</i> (Ahmed et al., 2022)</p> <p>Facilitation in Terrestrial Ecosystems <i>"Co-creation of seed processing techniques during a community workshop....Local training and workshops that provide young people with opportunities to learn...."</i> (Montenegro et al., 2024) <i>"Teachers and program partners played essential background roles by organizing restoration projects"</i> (Chawla, 2023)</p>

	<p><i>"The government has also established public employment service agencies which provide skill training for farmers...."</i></p> <p>Facilitation in Mixed Ecosystems <i>"In Year 5 of the Tsitsa Project, Community Liaison Officers were employed. The Community Liaison Officers participated in training and practiced skills related to land and water governance, communication and community engagement, and citizen science." (Qiu et al., 2022)</i></p>
<p>Bioaffiliation</p>	<p>Marine Ecosystems <i>"Managing and caring for a living and dynamic Country is at the heart of wellbeing for Indigenous peoples; harm to Country degrades Malgana identity, Aboriginal identity, and Australian identity." (Sinclair et al., 2024)</i> <i>"Of participants, 86 % had a moderate or high concern for Harbour health, with urban water pollution listed as the main environmental concern (47 % of participants)....I would support restoration in every part of Sydney Harbour" or "To restore what has been lost" (Howie et al., 2024)</i> <i>"Coastal fishing is considered an integral part of Finnish cultural heritage." (González-Torres et al., 2024)</i> <i>"I have lived at Parham for almost 40 years. I love the whole coastline; the changing seasons, birdlife, fishing, and crabbing. I visited the beaches with my parents who are now no longer here. I have many memories to share with the next generation." (Clarke et al., 2021)</i></p> <p>Terrestrial Ecosystems <i>"Novella Carpenter's urban farm brought people together... 'This place reminds me of my grandma,' he tells her. 'Everything's so growing.'" (Zytkoskee et al., 2024)</i> <i>"Festivities and trees are inextricably linked. They have, e.g., a yearly ritual of hunting after worshipping the forest God....These people have thus established a sustainable connection with the local forest ecosystem." (Haq et al., 2023)</i> <i>"Planting trees represented a commitment to way of life and to the community: 'Somos unidos' (we are united) was often repeated in reference to working together to plant trees and improve farming....Today, many tree-planting residents self-define as 'ecologistas' – stewards of the land." (Wilson and Coomes, 2019)</i></p> <p>Fresh Water and mixed ecosystems <i>"The lake that has now been created was already known to the ancients, as the historical archives prove." (Impedovo et al., 2024)</i> <i>"There's the wow, our soul is with these creatures too, and we're supposed to take care of them'...."A student in California shared: 'I really feel free and peaceful where it was all watery and wild'" (Chawla, 2023)</i></p>
<p>Material abduction</p>	<p>Marine Ecosystems</p>

	<p><i>"The cultivation potential of three additional species, specifically Caulerpa racemosa, Gracilariopsis longissimi, and Catenella nipae, has been confirmed solely through experimental means" (Asaduzzaman et al., 2024)</i></p> <p><i>"Few farmers are also trying cage culture of seaweed, sea bass, sea bream, and oysterall these are done experimentally...." (Ahmed et al., 2022)</i></p> <p>Terrestrial Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"A set of research projects have identified germination traits, tested and adapted direct seeding techniques, and monitored areas under restoration." (Montenegro et al., 2024)</i></p> <p><i>"Our modified hessian snaggers increased the edges available for snagging seedlings and were lighter and easier to handle than bags. They are worth further investigation." (Sinclair et al., 2024)</i></p> <p><i>"Though not all efforts are successful, the general attitude is one of optimistic intervention, and even failures have the byproduct of increased knowledge and understanding of an ecosystem....Restorationists rely on historical data, but they also must adapt to changing environmental conditions...." (Zytkoskee et al., 2024)</i></p> <p>Mixed Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"At times calling themselves 'living labs,' the communities also emphasize learning and knowledge production through structured design and skills courses along with monitoring, research and evaluation efforts." (Sides, 2023)</i></p>
<p>Relational intercession</p>	<p>Marine Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"Collaborations between community groups, farmers, corporations, governments, and researchers help negotiate divergent restoration interests and enable the formulation of collective priorities and strategies." (Montenegro et al., 2024)</i></p> <p><i>"Collaborations between community groups, farmers, corporations, governments, and researchers help negotiate divergent restoration interests and enable the formulation of collective priorities and strategies." (Howie et al., 2024)</i></p> <p>Terrestrial Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"Governmental programs such as PROCODES and PROREST actively engage local populations in land management, sustainable resource utilization, protection, and restoration efforts." (González-Torres et al., 2024)</i></p> <p><i>"The corridor was planned in collaboration with the local community and State Forest Departments through 'Connecting Landscapes, Empowering People, and Protecting Elephants' as part of Wildlife Trust of India's Land Securement Strategy." (Haq et al., 2023)</i></p> <p>Mixed Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"Teachers formed partnerships with environmental organizations, government agencies, and universities that provided curricula and technical support, making students' engagement in restoration work possible" (Chawla, 2023)</i></p>

	<p><i>"In practice, the EC advances these ambitions principally through the provision of finance through various instruments and funds, and by having its officials promote awareness of the Mission at Member State level and across the different branches of the EC."</i> (Whyte et al., 2024)</p>
Discursive grounding	<p>Marine Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"Scenario 2 uses social media platforms to launch targeted campaigns informing the public about marine debris's direct and indirect impacts....Media coverage can bring attention to the issue through news stories, documentaries, and social media posts that highlight the impacts of marine debris on the environment and human health."</i> (Koko et al., 2024)</p> <p><i>"Knowledge sharing with the local community via Science talks, Living and museum collections,....Knowledge sharing through story telling....The Wirriya Jalyanu (seagrass) Festival and science talks were attended by more than 140 Shark Bay residents and visitors of all ages....The festival theme of 'Art meets Science' was designed to appeal to a wider audience, sharing knowledge of Sea Country through a mix of science, culture, language, and artistic activities....Workshops included communication with media (filming and interviews)."</i> (Sinclair et al., 2024)</p> <p>Terrestrial Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"We further stress that any knowledge exchange must be conducted primarily via careful listening and appropriate engagement in a way that supports indigenous leadership and communication customs."</i> (Haq et al., 2023)</p> <p>Fresh Water and Mixed Ecosystems</p> <p><i>"The imaginary of the more than human commons may travel – via scientific papers, videos on the project website, and presentations like these – into the imaginations and regulatory practices of people seeking to restore other rivers and wetlands."</i> (Woelfle-Erskine, 2018)</p> <p><i>"Teachers told stories—for example, about the relationship between monarch butterflies and milkweeds. These stories gave direction to students' outing to scatter milkweed seeds....Encouraging students to share their stories of their experiences, in turn, created a space 'to talk about'...."</i> (Chawla, 2023)</p> <p><i>"Media tactics are no secret to the general public... The more extreme the methods employed, the more likely people are to question the possibility of manipulation."</i> (Zytkoskee et al., 2024)</p> <p><i>"In the case of Ecosystem Restoration Communities, explicit and implicit theories of change are shared through the movement's main website."</i> (Sides, 2023)</p> <p><i>"Narratives or storytelling as a methodological framework can empower individuals, communities, and networks, and serve as an alternative that respects the complexity, social fabric, geography, and socio-political contexts of people and places....The documentary enabled citizens to convey richer and multisensory messages and experiences which could not have been expressed in texts (e.g., folk songs)."</i> (Mehmood et al., 2019)</p>

Appendix 7. Gioia Data Structure Table

First-Order Concepts	Second-Order Themes	Aggregated Dimensions
<p>Fisheries Leader Advisor's Personal Vision for Mussel Farming</p> <p>Fisheries Leader Advisor Recognized Project Manager's Skills in Innovation</p> <p>Fisheries Leader Advisor Wanted to Recruit Project Manager Earlier</p> <p>Change in the Industry Always Starts with a Few Pioneers</p> <p>Change in the Fishing Industry Always Starts with a Few Pioneers</p> <p>First Few People Should Get Involved and Start to Build Demand</p> <p>Key Person or Persons Need to Start Something New to Drive Others</p> <p>Roles of Leaders and Models Depend on the Location and Community</p> <p>Project Leadership and Responsibilities</p> <p>Need for a Strategic Approach</p> <p>Success of Mussel Farming Depends on Key Individuals in the Community</p> <p>Goal Is to Develop Duck Mussel Farming</p> <p>Goal to Develop Duck Mussel Production Systems</p> <p>Identifying Candidate Species for Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland</p> <p>Long-Term Goal Is Developing a Production Model for Duck Mussels</p> <p>Identifying Regenerative Ocean Farming Possibilities in Finland</p>	<p>Strategic Visioning and Leadership</p>	<p>Strategic Foundations for Regenerative Practice</p>
<p>Building a Proper Network</p> <p>Connection to the Project Through Existing Networks</p> <p>Good Collaboration with Facilitators</p> <p>Long-Term Collaboration with Fisheries Advisor</p> <p>Managing Multiple Related Projects</p> <p>Need for a Collaborative Network</p> <p>Relationship with Fisheries Advisor Through Fisheries and Network</p> <p>Project Partners Across Multiple Countries</p> <p>Chef as an Ambassador for Finnish Cuisine</p> <p>The Fisherman Considers Himself a Pioneer in Innovation</p> <p>Acting as an Ambassador for the Project</p> <p>Working with International Partners</p> <p>Organization Location</p> <p>Purpose of Cool Blue Platform</p>	<p>Network and Collaborative Efforts</p>	

<p>The Cool Blue Project and Cool Baltic Project Other Projects Organisation Engaged With European Union's Role in Ecosystem Restoration Exploring Funding Opportunities Collaboratively Hiring Someone for Further Investigation</p>	
<p>Need to Increase Duck Mussel Production Aktion Österbotten Goal Is Food Production Now Trying to Understand How to Grow from That First Reproduction Stage Fishermen Are Important for Testing, Not Production As a Fisherman, Mussels Farming Is Not a Challenge Role in the Mussel Project Planning for Spring and Summer Activities Hatchery Development Is Key for Scaling Mussel Farming Hatchery at the University for Pearl Mussels Not Just Waiting for Lab-Based Hatchery Exploring Natural Hatchery Locations Trying to Develop a New Hatchery Method Without Fish</p>	<p>Production Infrastructure and Strategic Planning</p>
<p>Project Is Still in Testing Phase Still in the Early Stages of Testing the Idea Developing Mussel Cages for Farming Site Selection for Mussel Farming Requires Consideration of Other Interests Site Selection for Mussel Placement – Depth, Protection, and Currents Finding Best Locations for Community Mussel Placement Choosing Locations for Community-Based Mussel Farming Requires Planning Coastal Waters Could Be Used for Rearing Mussels Before Commercial Production Controlled Placement of Mussels to Improve Survival Potential Hatchery Locations Floating Island Concept for Mussel Farming Potential for Controlled Farming Using Bags or Containers Importance of Quantitative Data to Show People the Results Need to Get Real Reports on How to Grow Mussels</p>	<p>Testing, Site Selection, and Experimental Foundations</p>

<p>Need for a Proof of Concept and Clear Guidelines for Fishermen Participation Applying for a Larger Research Project With a University Applying for Funding to Support Research Potential for Funding in Regenerative Projects</p>		
<p>Duck Mussels Grow Quite Fast Compared to Other Mussels Mussel Growth Is Very Slow Duck Mussels Already Exist in Nature Salinity Affect on Mussel Growth Influence of Salinity on Mussels Mussels Enter Dormancy in Cold Temperatures Negative Environmental Factors Affecting Mussels Negative Effects of Acidification on Mussels Confirmation That Ecosystems Have a Mussel Limit All Mussel Species Play a Similar Role in Ecosystems Mussel Quality Based on Environment High Filtration Capacity of Duck Mussels Distinguishing Between Duck Mussels & Swan Mussels Duck and Swan Mussels as Best Options Human Activities and Mussel Population Decline High Natural Mussel Populations in Some Lakes Natural Spread of Duck Mussels Reproduction and Life Cycle of Duck Mussels Complexity of Duck Mussel Reproduction Understanding Mussel Reproduction Cycle Growth Cycle of Duck Mussels Method to Count the Age of a Mussel Feeding and Growth of Juvenile Mussels Mussels' Adaptation to Environmental Conditions Mussels' Response to Pollution and Oxygen Levels Fish Farms and Hatcheries as Solutions for Growing Mussels Potential for Regenerative Ocean Farming Beyond Duck Mussels Alternative to Hatchery by Putting Mussels from Nature to Coastal Areas</p>	<p>Building Biological and Reproductive Knowledge of Duck Mussels</p>	<p>Local Ecological Knowledge Formation</p>

<p>Can Use Alternative Mussel Species for Regeneration Finding Best Areas in Finland for Growing Dark Mussels Finding Best Conditions for Mussels Intended for Consumption Suitability of Finnish Coastal Waters for Mussels Finland Has Potential for Regenerative Ocean Farming Despite Challenges Status of Dark Mussels in Finland vs. Europe Low Salinity in Finnish Waters Aquaculture Is Emerging in Finland Source of Mother Mussels for Reproduction Alternative Mussel Species Can Be Used for Regeneration</p>		
<p>Mussel Beds as Biodiversity Hotspots Mussel Shells Providing Habitat for Other Species Mussels Mixing Sediment and Enhancing Oxygen Levels Mussels Reducing Harmful Bacteria in Water Mussels' Role in Removing Fish Pathogens Mussels Reducing Fish Parasites Nutrient Removal from Water Ecosystems Sediment Modification and Water Quality Improvement of Duck Mussels Mussels in Lake and River Restoration Projects Duck Mussel Farming Is Equally Interesting for Food and Water Regeneration Combining Mussels & Floating Gardens for Pollution Control Using Mussels in Fish Farms to Support Fish Health Potential Health Benefits for Fish from Being Near Mussels Applications of Duck Mussel Farming Alternative Uses for Duck Mussels Beyond Food Using Mussels in Graveyard Monitoring Water Cleaning Effectiveness Hatchery vs. Wild Mussels' Filtration Efficiency Growth Timeline for Water Cleaning Use</p>	<p>Building Environmental and Ecosystem Services Knowledge of Duck Mussels</p>	
<p>Duck Mussels Have a Muddy Taste When Taken from the Bottom</p>	<p>Building Sensory and Culinary</p>	

<p>Change in Mussel Flavor Based on Environment Location Impacts Mussel Taste, Open Waters Produce Better Flavor Mussels Must Be Lifted from the Mud for Good Taste Mussels Absorb the Flavor of Their Environment Mussels Accumulating Heavy Metals So Not Edible Surface Placement of Mussels May Cause Damage Mussels Survive After Being Moved Sterile Environments Reduce Mussel Flavor Optimal Environmental Conditions for Filtration Put In Sea, Tastes Like Ocean</p>	<p>Knowledge of Duck Mussels</p>
<p>Continual Learning & Problem Solver Regular Meetings to Share Knowledge Collaboration with Other Experts on Water Cleaning Research on Duck Mussel Reproduction by University Learning About Duck Mussel Biology from the Seminar Fish Farmers Assisted in Relocation of Mussels Fisherman Has Helped with Experimenting Collaboration with Different Stakeholders Like Aquaculture, Fishermen, and Youth Projects Fisherman's Role in the Experiment: Transporting, Equipment, and Deploying Mussels Following the Project and Open to Helping in Future Testing How Mussels Should Be Handed to Communities from Specialists Introduction to Duck Mussels Through the Project People Accidentally Finding Mussels While Swimming Introducing Dark Mussels to a New Coastal Area First Thing Was Testing Different Cage Models for Duck Mussels Experimenting with New Cage Designs for Next Season Testing & Deploying Mussel Cages in Spring</p>	<p>Collaborative Experimentations and Knowledge Co-creation</p>

<p>Testing Natural Growth & Survival of Mussels Testing Different Depths for Mussel Growth Is the Plan for 2025 Find a Method to Get the Mussels as Fast as Possible Test to Create Natural Hatchery Using Nature to Accelerate the Hatchery Process More Effective Alternative to Lab Hatcheries Lantern Net Model Proves Most Effective Size & Structure of Mussel Cages Exploring Alternative Uses for Duck Mussels Testing Nutrient Content & Applications of Duck Mussels Importance of Studying Nutritional Content and Health Benefits Investigating Mussel Taste & Quality Lab Testing and Researching Duck Mussels One Year of Testing Needed for Initial Results Using a Secchi Disk to Measure Water Clarity Combining Natural & Semi-Laboratory Methods</p>		
<p>Finnish Connection to the Sea Community Awareness & Interest in Regenerative Practices Community Interest in the Environment Interest in Healthier, More Sustainable Food Production Interest in Regenerative Thinking Local Memory and Motivation for Restoration Community Engagement in Environmental Restoration Potential Positive Environmental Impact of Mussel Farming Mussels Enhance Ecosystem Balance & Function Public Concern About Algae Blooms in Lakes Preventing Algae Blooms Using Mussels & Gardens Improving Biodiversity and Getting Food at the Same Time Interest from Local Fish Farmers Farmers & Municipalities Might Participate for Environmental Reasons</p>	<p>Emotional, Cultural, and Environmental Drivers for Engagement</p>	<p>Motivations, Mechanisms, and Pathways for Community Engagement</p>

<p>Good PR for Fish Farmers to Reverse Their Environmental Damage Willingness to Innovate to Stay Competitive</p>	
<p>Excitement Around Pioneering a New Industry People Are Curious About Farming Duck Mussels Interest in Producing Food in a Regenerative Way Commitment to Local Ingredients Interest in New Challenges Curiosity About New Species That Can Survive in Low-Salinity Waters Interest in Trying Duck Mussels Interest in Trying New Things Interested and Not Afraid To Try New Things Growing Interest in Duck Mussel Interest of Fishers and Farmers in Duck Mussels Losing Previous Job & Transitioning to Regenerative Work Restaurants May Be Interested for Branding and Storytelling People Liked the Taste of Duck Mussels The Mussel Tasting Event Was Inspirational Role of Public Interest in Determining Future Directions Increasing Consumer Awareness of Sustainability Some Enthusiasts May Be Interested</p>	<p>Curiosity, Novelty, and Excitement as a Local Product</p>
<p>Economic Incentives as a Motivator to Grow Mussels Fisherman Will Be Interested if They Know That Mussels Will Be an Extra Income Fishermen Would Be Interested if It Adds Value to Their Business Participation Depends on Profit Main Interest in Expanding Product Portfolio Beyond Fish Regenerative Ocean Farming as More of a Commercial Thing Than a Community Thing Motivation as Balancing Practical Work & Research Limited Involvement from Other Fishermen So Far Different Motivations for Community Involvement Can't Force Communities to Engage</p>	<p>Economic, Feasibility, and New Business Opportunity</p>

Participation in International Seminar on Ocean Regeneration		
<p>Getting the Message to Public</p> <p>Future Media Engagement on Duck Mussels</p> <p>Local Newspaper Coverage</p> <p>National Media Coverage</p> <p>Media Interest in Mussel Project</p> <p>Openness to Publicity and Awareness Efforts</p> <p>Sharing Success Stories to Gain Public Support</p> <p>Spreading the Word Is Important</p> <p>Participating in Public Events</p> <p>Stakeholder Engagement Through Site Visits and Media</p> <p>Organizing Public Demonstrations and Educational Initiatives</p> <p>Plan to Create a Centralized Demonstration Site</p> <p>Practical Demonstrations of the Process</p> <p>Creating an Aquarium to Show Mussels to the Public</p> <p>Inviting Media to Tasting Event</p> <p>Raising Awareness of Duck Mussels</p> <p>Need for Scientific Information to Convince the Public to Eat Mussels</p> <p>Need for Training & Education for Community Involvement</p> <p>Need More Knowledge to Get More Involved</p> <p>Start Engaging Communities with Basic Guidelines, Purpose, and Information</p> <p>Training Needed for Communities on How to Handle Baby Mussels Before Releasing Them</p> <p>Organized Help on How to Get Mussels for Farming</p> <p>How Mussels Should Be Handed to Communities from Specialists</p> <p>Communities Can Just Put the Mussels in Water, No Take Care Needed</p> <p>Using Children as a Pathway to Community Engagement</p> <p>Local Community Members Are Better Suited for Farming</p> <p>Community-Based Models Could Be Revived</p> <p>Engaging More People to Participate</p> <p>Have Different Ways of Motivating and Engaging Communities</p>	Public Outreach, Awareness, Education, and Sensory Engagement Strategies	
Duck Mussels as a Locally Sourced Seafood	Gastronomic Framing and	Pathways for the Emergence of

Duck Mussels for Environmental and Culinary Use	Cultural Narrative Building	Regenerative Business Models
<p>Mussels as Food</p> <p>Mussels Are an Environmentally Friendly Protein Source</p> <p>Mussels as an Easy-to-Cook Ingredient</p> <p>Mussels can be used in Different Ways</p> <p>Potential for Different Cooking Methods for Duck Mussels</p> <p>Nutritional Benefits of Mussels</p> <p>Taste of Duck Mussels</p> <p>Texture and Cooking Comparison to Other Shell Food</p> <p>Flavour of the Mussel Matters More than the Texture</p> <p>Importance of Mussel Size for Cooking</p> <p>Mussel Sausages in Post-War Germany</p> <p>Mussels Having a Neutral Taste</p> <p>Preference for Locally Produced Seasonal Ingredients</p> <p>Duck Mussels as a New Food in Finland</p> <p>Duck Mussels as a Seasonal Product</p> <p>Duck Mussels as a Niche Product with Limited Appeal</p> <p>Comparing Duck Mussels Novelty to Other Foods</p> <p>Comparing Meat to Seafood</p> <p>Shift in Finnish Cuisine Toward Seafood</p> <p>Younger Generations Are More Open to New Foods</p> <p>Guest Reaction to the Mussel Tasting Event</p> <p>Guests Being Excited at the Tasting Event</p> <p>Testing Duck Mussel Taste With Public and Restaurants</p> <p>Chef's First Impression of Duck Mussels</p> <p>Overall Positive Impression of Duck Mussels from Chef</p> <p>Positive Feedback from Chef on Duck Mussel Taste from His Fish Farm</p> <p>Chef's Limited Experience With Shellfish & Interest in Experimenting</p> <p>Restaurants as the Main Market</p> <p>Willingness of Chefs to Work with Mussels</p> <p>If The Price is ok Chefs Will Try It</p> <p>Chefs Are Key to Market Creation and Promotion</p> <p>Chef's Effort in Promoting Finnish Products</p> <p>Role of Chefs and Restaurants in Creating Demand</p> <p>Testing and Introducing to Restaurants</p>		

<p>Why Chef Was Chosen for the Mussel Project Collaboration with Chefs and Restaurants to Build Demand Expectation That Chefs in Finland Will Be Interested Expectation That Mussels Will Reach the Market Quickly Testing Mussels in a Restaurant Possible Need to Modify Cooking Process for Duck Mussels Ensuring Food Safety Through Cooking Optimal Conditions for Mussels Meant for Food</p>		
<p>Possibility of Using Cleaned Mussels for Food Depends on Water Source No Hygiene Concerns About Mussels from Fish Farms No Known Health Risks From Eating Duck Mussels Extra Income with Little Effort with Mussel Farming Mussel Farming Requires Less Daily Work Than Fishing Workload of Mussel Farming Compared to Fishing Ease of Mussel Farming Compared to Fishing Equipment Setup Existing Fishing Infrastructure Can Be Used for Mussel Farming Duck Mussel Farming Needs to Be Economically Viable Long-Term Business Potential of Duck Mussel Farming Duck Mussels as a Protein Source Should Be Cheap Mussels Don't Weigh Much So Will Need a Big Volume for Profit Need to Do Calculations on Pricing Profitability and Market Size for Mussels Will Be the Main Challenge Uncertainty in Texture and Cooking Methods and Need More Experimentation Need to Find How Fast They Grow to Commercialize Investment Requirements for Commercial Mussel Farming Harvesting Efficiency of Mussels If Mussels Can Be Grown Commercial Then Fishermen Will Be Interested</p>	<p>Economic Viability and Requirements Needed for Commercialization</p>	

<p>In Short Term It Is Fun but In Long Term There Needs to Be Profits Potential for Large-Scale Duck Mussel Production Without Environmental Harm Mussel Price Should Be Cheap as a Protein Source Small-Scale Farming Might Start Next Year Scaling Up Mussel Farming Would Require More Cages, Not Larger Ones Scalability and Market Penetration Dependent on Price Factors to Consider for Commercialization Need to Differentiate Mussels Used for Cleaning vs. Those for Food Limited Evidence of Duck Mussels as Food Evidence of Duck Mussel as a Food More Research Needed on Duck Mussels More Research Is Needed Before Commercialization Testing for Pollutants and Nutrient Content in Mussels Positive Lab Test Results Need Further Investigations on Novelty Future of Duck Mussels as a Business Depends on Reproduction Success Uncertainty About Production Cost Uncertainty About Large-Scale Market for Mussels</p>	
<p>Different Business Models Based on Different Interests Community vs. Business-Oriented Mussel Farming Models Need for Hybrid or Alternative Models for Community Mussel Farming Public-Private Partnership or Joint Venture Hatcheries Aligning Mussel Farming with EU Agricultural Subsidies Seeking Larger Project Opportunities Scaling Up & Finding the Right Expertise Potential for Mussels as a Global Protein Solution Potential Use of Mussels in Fish Farming as Compensation Models Potential Connection Between Mussels and Fish Farms Potential Interest from Fish Farming Industry Potential Interest from Other Fishermen in Mussel Farming</p>	<p>Entrepreneurial Imagination and Opportunity Recognition</p>

<p>Framing Regenerative Aquaculture as a Job Creation Opportunity Discovering Job Opportunity in Regenerative Ocean Farming Interest in Duck Mussel Farming as a New Business Opportunity</p>		
Cross-Cutting Theme		
<p>Unique Challenges of Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland Budget requirements for hatchery No Environmental Risks Identified Project Is in Early Stages, No Commercial Involvement Yet To Engage Fishermen in Farming Need a Production Model for Duck Mussels Not Many Are Actively Involved Not Important for Community Engagement Fishermen Will Only Participate if Paid Fisherman Are Not the First Target Group for Production Low Demand for Mussels in Finnish Households Mussels Are Not a Traditional Finnish Food Culturally Not Known to Consume Mussels in Finland Duck Mussels Are Not Traditionally Consumed in Europe Finnish Consumers Are Conservative About Eating Mussels Lack of Awareness About Finnish Ingredients Lack of Cultural Habit of Eating Mussels Mussels Are Not a Part of Finnish Food Culture Seafood Is Not Common in Finland Need for Sustainable Cultivation Instead of Wild Harvesting Not Sure of the Risks from Seals and Seabirds for Mussels Agricultural and Forestry Activities Contribute to Nutrient Pollution Aquaculture Is Needed Because Can't Rely on Fish Concern About Overharvesting and Sustainability Concern About the State of the Marine Ecosystem Concerns Over Decreasing Fish Availability Declining Mussel Populations & Habitat Destruction</p>		<p>Barriers, Tensions & Structural Limitations</p>

Duck Mussels Are Not Visible for People
Novel Food Is Not the Main Thing
Anticipated Future Commercialization
Timeline of Duck Mussels
Anyway Can't Sell
Challenges with Authorities and Regulatory Approval
Current Lack of Specific Legal Framework for Mussel Farming
EU Funding Important for Fisheries, Not Sure Whether It's the Same With Mussels
Finland Has Strict Permit Regulations for Coastal Activities
Frustration with Novel Food Legalization Process
Funding Challenges and FLAG Project Involvement
Government Leases Are Required for Offshore Areas
Importance of Quantitative Data for Funding
Importance of Quantitative Data for Scaling and Regulation
Is Novel Food Approval Needed
It Will Take at Least Three Years to Write a Farming Guide
Lack of Clear Farming Guidelines
Legal Rights Were There as a Fisherman
Helped in Site Selection for Initial Experiment
More Practical Testing Needed Before Wider Adoption
Need Experts to Investigate Novel Food Process
Need for Hatchery Funding
Need for Legal Approval Before Commercialization
Need for Subsidies to Support Early Adoption of Mussel Farming
No Clear Process for Novel Food Approval
No Limit on Duck Mussels in Fish Farms, Just Area Restrictions
No Proper Hatchery for Dark Mussels Yet
No Proper Mapping of Mussels
No Special License Needed, Just Water Permits
Not Farming Yet
Novel Food Approval is Expensive & Time-Consuming
Novel Food Legalization is a Formality, Not a Major Issue

Possible Need for Regulatory Action Only if
 Complaints Arise
 Regulatory Authorities Avoiding the Duck
 Mussel Novel Food Topic
 So Far Don't Know How the Real
 Commercial Duck Mussel Production Would
 Look Like or Happen
 Uncertain About Commercial Farming
 Participation But Have a Positive Attitude
 Uncertainty of Getting Novel Food Approval
 Uncertainty About Why Mussels Are Not
 Eaten
 Uncertainty Around Duck Mussel Farming &
 Commercial Uses
 Uncertainty Around the Novel Food Status of
 Duck Mussels
 Water Ownership and Permit Requirements
 Vary by Location in Finland
 Challenges in Achieving Consistent Flavor of
 Mussels
 Challenges in Early Growth Stages of
 Mussels
 Challenges in Handling and Securing the
 Mussel Cages
 Challenges in Raising Dark Mussels in
 Controlled Conditions
 Challenges of Growing Freshwater Mussels
 in Coastal Finland
 Challenges of Growing Mussels in
 Laboratory Settings
 Concerns About Mussels Absorbing
 Contaminants
 Difficulty in Measuring the Water-Cleaning
 Effect of Mussels
 Effective Reproduction Is the Main Challenge
 Finding Suitable Locations for Mussel
 Farming Takes Time
 No Noticeable Growth in Two Months
 Removal of Mussels Due to Ice Formation
 Uncertainty About Mussel Availability
 Uncertainty About Optimal Depth for Mussel
 Growth So Experimenting This Next Season
 Uncertainty About the Worth of Fish
 Hatchery Method's Success
 Uncertainty of How Exactly Mussels
 Handling Is Done
 Visual Water Clean Monitoring Challenges
 Can Take Mussels from Nature in Some
 Cases

<p>Fishing Rights and Their Potential Role in Mussel Farming Getting Mussels from Nature Not a Long-Term Solution Open Waters Are Unsuitable for Community-Based Mussel Farming Possibility of Getting the Novel Food Approval</p>	
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Appendix 8. Interview Questions for Fisheries Leader Advisor, and Project Manager

1. Setting the scene – Background information: Type of organization

1. Can you introduce yourself briefly? What is your main job, role and/or function?
2. When and how did you become involved with this project? Can you tell me more about how your association or organization started? What inspired its creation? What motivated your association with this project?
3. What are your main activities or goals?
4. How does your association get funding or support for these regenerative activities? What is your annual budget, and who are the most active contributors to the organization?
5. What is your “regeneration thesis”, i.e. can you talk us through some of the main ways in which the project helps with regeneration?

2. Business and economic elements

6. Can you explain your key products or services? Do you produce any byproducts from your harvest?
7. We are curious about hands-on activities. What part does personal involvement play in regeneration? How frequently do you engage in hands-on activities like harvesting?
8. Talk us through your future plans for developing your project further. What comes next? What’s the ultimate vision? How would you know that vision has been achieved?

3. Community and people elements

9. What motivates you to engage in ocean farming? What drives your passion for this work?
10. How do you feel about the impact of this project on your community? What key values guide or reflect your commitment to the community?
12. How does the local community get involved in this project, and how do they benefit from your activities?
13. Please walk us through the interactions with the community: in what specific ways is the community involved?
14. Do you have plans to expand your work and involve new partners, communities, or stakeholders? Do you factor in any specific constraints or contingencies as part of these growth plans?

4. Ecological and regenerative elements

15. How do you feel about your work in ocean farming, especially your connection to the sea, and the impact it has on the ecology? What key values guide your work, and how do they reflect your commitment to the natural environment?
16. What other considerations does your work offer to the regeneration of marine ecosystems?

Appendix 9. Interview Questions for Fishermen

1. Introduction & Background

1. Can you tell me a bit about yourself and your work as a fisherman?
2. How did you first hear about the idea of working with duck mussels?
3. What made you interested in helping with these experiments?

2. Involvement in Duck Mussel Experiments

4. Can you describe what you have done so far with duck mussels?
5. Have you worked directly with Jonas on this? How?
6. What were your first thoughts when you started working with duck mussels?
7. What challenges have you noticed when handling or working with them?
8. Would you be interested in working with duck mussels again? If so, in what way?
9. From your experience, how do duck mussels compare to other shellfish or aquatic species you've worked with?
10. Do you think there is a future for duck mussels as a business in Finland? Why or why not?

3. Community Involvement & Fishing Industry Perspective

11. Do you see other fishermen becoming interested in duck mussels in the future? Why or why not?
12. What do you think would make fishermen more willing to work with duck mussels?
13. How do you think duck mussels could fit into Finland's fishing industry?
14. Are there any concerns fishermen might have about working with duck mussels?

4. Challenges & Future Potential

15. What do you think are the biggest challenges in using duck mussels as part of fishing or aquaculture?
16. Apart from the legal restrictions, what other barriers do you think might prevent duck mussels from being widely used?
17. If regulations allowed, do you think fishermen would be open to harvesting duck mussels? Why or why not?

5. Future Outlook & Final Thoughts

18. What do you think needs to happen for duck mussels to become a common part of Finnish fishing?
19. Do you think there is a future for regenerative ocean farming in Finland? Why or why not?

Appendix 10. Interview Questions for the Local Chef

1. Introduction & Background

1. Can you tell me a bit about yourself and your journey as a chef?
2. How did you first hear about duck mussels and their potential as food?
3. What made you interested or motivated in trying duck mussels at your restaurant?

2. Experience with Duck Mussels & the Tasting Event

4. Can you walk me through the process you followed in preparing duck mussels for the tasting event?
5. What were your first impressions of working with duck mussels in the kitchen?
6. What do you feel about the guest's reaction to the duck mussels at the event?
7. Compared to other seafood, how do you see duck mussels in terms of taste, texture, and cooking potential?

3. Community Involvement & Restaurant Perspective

8. How did you get involved with Jonas in this initiative?
9. What was your main motivation for taking part in the event?
10. Would you say that you are actively involved in the regenerative movement, or do you see yourself more as a supporter? Why?
11. Would you be interested in working with duck mussels again? If so, in what way?
12. In your opinion, do you think other chefs or restaurants would be open to using duck mussels, after legalization process? Why or why not?
13. What do you think could encourage more chefs to try duck mussels on their menus?

4. Challenges & Business Perspective

14. If duck mussels were legalized as a novel food, do you think they could become a common ingredient in Finnish cuisine?
15. Apart from the legal restrictions, what other barriers do you think might affect the adoption of duck mussels in restaurants? (e.g., sourcing, availability, customer interest)
16. In Finland, mussels are not a common ingredient compared to other seafood. Do you think this could make it harder for duck mussels to gain acceptance? Why or why not?
17. If regulations allowed, would you consider featuring duck mussels on your menu? What factors would influence that decision?
18. Do you think restaurants can play a role in introducing people to new and sustainable ingredients like duck mussels?

5. Future Outlook & Final Thoughts

19. What steps do you think need to be taken for duck mussels to become a widely accepted ingredient in Finland, other than the legalization part?
20. What advice would you give to other chefs or restaurants considering using duck mussels?

Appendix 11. Interview Questions for Fisheries Leader Advisor on Novel Food Process

1. About the Novel Food Process

1. We heard from Anita that you guys had a very productive discussion two weeks back about the Novel Food status for duck mussels. Can you please tell us a little about it and any progress you have made?
2. Have you come across any evidence or examples of duck mussels being used as food anywhere in the world, either now or in the past?
3. From your experience so far, what's the biggest hurdle in getting duck mussels approved as a novel food?
4. Are there any pilot projects or ongoing applications looking into this already?

2. Importance of Novel Food Status for Community Involvement

5. In your opinion, how important is it to get duck mussels approved as a novel food for local communities to engage in regenerative practices?
6. Do you think the lack of legal status is a major barrier to community participation?
7. Could community-driven projects help with data collection or pilot farming to support the Novel Food application?

3. Market Potential & Consumer Interest

8. How do you see the market potential for duck mussels here in Finland or in the EU?
9. Have you received any feedback from consumers or the chef, especially after the tasting event?
10. Do duck mussels have unique selling points, such as nutritional or culinary benefits? Anita mentioned researching this, what are your thoughts?
11. Do you foresee any cultural or culinary challenges in promoting duck mussels to Finnish consumers?

4. Community Involvement & Local Opportunities

12. How do you think local communities, such as fishermen, could get involved in duck mussel farming?
13. Are there any farmers or community members currently involved or planning to get involved in duck mussel farming?
14. What social or economic benefits could community-led duck mussel farming create for the Ostrobothnia region?
15. What opportunities could this create for local businesses if duck mussels become a recognized novel food?

5. Environmental Impact

16. Are there any potential environmental challenges with farming duck mussels that we should be aware of?
17. Are there any known environmental risks with introducing duck mussel farming to local waters?

6. Collaboration, Policy, and Support

18. What kind of support, like policy changes, funding, or partnerships, would help move the Novel Food application forward?
19. If this project succeeds, what do you think would be the next steps for scaling up community-driven duck mussel farming?

7. Final Thoughts

20. Overall, how optimistic are you about the chances of duck mussels becoming an approved novel food in Finland or the EU?

Appendix 12. Interview Questions for Biologist Researcher

1. Setting the Scene and Understanding Duck Mussels

1. Can you introduce yourself and tell us a bit about your research on mussels?
2. What kind of work do you do with Akiton österbotten regarding duck mussels?
3. What are some of the key biological characteristics of duck mussels, and why do you think it is the best type of mussel to be grown in Finland?

2. Duck Mussel Water Cleaning Function and Factors Affecting It

4. How do Duck Mussels contribute to water quality and biodiversity?
5. Do duck mussels have any special abilities or advantages in water filtration when compared to other mussel species?
6. Do you have any statistics or research findings on how much water a single duck mussel can filter per day, or any other interesting statistics?
7. Have you done research on what specific pollutants or nutrients duck mussels help remove from the water? For example, do they filter out nitrogen, phosphorus, heavy metals, or even microplastics?
8. What environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, salinity, oxygen levels) optimize the water-cleaning efficiency of duck mussels?
9. Are there any external factors that negatively impact their filtration ability, such as pollution, water flow, or seasonal changes?
10. How do different types of water bodies, like freshwater lakes, brackish waters, or coastal areas, affect their filtration capacity?
11. Are there known differences in water-cleaning effectiveness between wild and hatchery-raised duck mussels?

3. The Hatchery & Cultivation Research

12. How do duck mussels reproduce, and what factors influence their life cycle in the wild?
13. What environmental conditions are most suitable for the survival and growth of duck mussels?

14. Do you have a hatchery at the University for the Duck mussels? Could you explain the research and work being done on duck mussel hatcheries?
15. What are the key challenges in breeding and raising duck mussels in a controlled environment?
16. How long does it take for hatchery-grown mussels to reach a size where they can be effectively used for water cleaning?
17. Are there specific techniques or innovations being developed to improve the cultivation of duck mussels?

4. Community Engagement & Practical Aspects of Farming Duck Mussels

18. If communities were to receive duck mussels from the hatchery, what are the key things they need to do to ensure successful farming?
19. What are the biggest challenges or risks for communities trying to grow and maintain duck mussels in their local waters?
20. What kind of maintenance or care do duck mussels require from farmers?
21. Can communities monitor the health and water-cleaning effectiveness of the mussels over time?
22. Would mussel farming be more effective in specific regions of Finland based on environmental conditions?
23. What knowledge and training would community members need before they can start farming duck mussels?

5. Duck Mussels as a Food Source

24. Have you done any research on having Duck mussels as a food source? For example, what are their key nutritional benefits?
25. If the community wants to use duck mussels both for water purification and as a food product, what additional steps would they need to take?